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Deliverable 1.3: Gap analysis of research ethics and integrity resources for R&I in general and new climate and environmental technologies in particular

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List of abbreviations

Table 1: List of abbreviations

CCS	Carbon Capture and Storage
COP	Conference of the Parties
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
ECOC	European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity
EGD	European Green Deal
ERA	European Research Area
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GMOs	Genetically Modified Organisms
HLEG-AI	High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
IoT	Internet of Things
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
R&I	Research and Innovation
RE	Research Ethics
RE4GREEN	Research Ethics and Integrity for the GREEN Transition
RI	Research Integrity
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
SAB	Stakeholder Advisory Board
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

RE4GREEN project summary

Environmental and climate-related challenges are global and reach all sectors of society. However, research and innovation (R&I) activities that address these challenges may carry substantial unintended implications. **RE4GREEN aims to contribute to a European Research Area ethics and integrity framework for R&I activities designed to reduce the risk from such implications and to support the transition to a sustainable economy and society as envisioned by the European Green Deal (EGD).** RE4GREEN will reflect diverse stakeholder views and relate them to cross-cutting environmental and climate-related ethics issues by applying a bottom-up Social Lab methodology. RE4GREEN's framework will consist of operational research ethics and integrity guidelines, recommendations, and training materials for researchers, ethics and integrity experts and advisors, and ethics reviewers to ensure R&I activities support the Green Transition.

This deliverable reviews existing research (RE) ethics and research integrity (RI) frameworks and guidelines as well as training materials and programmes on environmental and climate ethics (findings from Tasks 1.4 and 1.3, respectively) within the European Research Area (ERA).

Task 1.4 focuses on assessing the comprehensiveness of existing RE&RI frameworks and guidelines in addressing environmental and climate concerns within research and innovation (R&I). By evaluating 213 frameworks, the analysis identified significant gaps, including the underrepresentation of critical environmental and climate ethical concerns, limited integration of environmental and climate justice, and insufficient inclusivity and consideration of disproportionately affected populations and indigenous perspectives in related issues. While some frameworks demonstrate emerging trends in embedding environmental ethics, most lack comprehensive guidance for addressing the ethical implications of new technologies and sustainability challenges. This gap analysis highlights the need to strengthen existing frameworks and will inform the development of operational guidelines (Task 3.2), ensuring that RE&RI resources effectively support the Green Transition in alignment with the European Green Deal objectives.

Task 1.3 provides an overview of existing training programmes and materials that address environmental and climate ethics. By analysing which ethical concepts and perspectives, ethical principles and values, research and innovation domains, and environmental and climate issues are represented within relevant resources, this task provides an understanding of the current education landscape and provides the basis for the development of new training micromodules and tailored pathways to engage diverse stakeholders and inspire environmentally- and climate-aware research (WP4). The gap analysis findings of 255 programs and 95 materials from across the ERA landscape highlight areas for closer alignment between RE&RI and environmental and climate guidance and education.

Overall, the objective of this deliverable is to provide a comprehensive analysis of existing RE&RI frameworks, guidelines, and training resources to identify gaps and opportunities for integrating environmental and climate ethics, thereby informing the development of tailored operational guidelines and educational pathways that support the Green Transition in alignment with the European Green Deal objectives in subsequent Work Packages (WPs).

1. Introduction

RE4GREEN is a Horizon Europe Coordination and Support Action (CSA) project designed to advance RE&RI frameworks to address environmental and climate challenges in R&I. Rooted in the principles of sustainability and intergenerational justice, the project contributes to the European Green Deal by promoting ethical accountability in R&I practices and supporting the Green Transition. This deliverable, D1.3, presents the outcomes of a comprehensive gap analysis of existing RE&RI frameworks and guidelines as well as training programs and materials (Tasks 1.4 and 1.3, respectively).

This deliverable evaluates how existing RE&RI guidelines and frameworks integrate environmental and climate considerations, identifies gaps and limitations in those guidelines and frameworks, and provides a foundation for developing operational guidelines and recommendations to improve RE&RI frameworks in subsequent work packages. It builds on earlier analyses conducted in Tasks 1.1 and 1.2, incorporating insights from a systematic review of key cross-cutting concepts and issues in climate and environmental ethics and relevant technologies. This gap analysis explores several dimensions, including the inclusion of key ethical principles, the applicability of RE&RI frameworks to emerging considerations such as sustainability goals and environmental protection imperatives, the comprehensiveness of the guidance provided by the frameworks, and the ability of these frameworks to address the needs of diverse stakeholder groups. Attention is also paid to disproportionately affected and indigenous populations as well as the unique ethical challenges posed by new climate and environmental technologies.

Similarly, and to ensure continuity between RE4GREEN project tasks, the review of training materials and programmes uses the same dimensions and prior insights to structure the gap analysis of these resources. This approach establishes a shared foundation for the assessment of guidelines, frameworks, training materials and programmes, allowing for a comparison of the key findings of each investigation and a holistic insight into how environmental and climate concerns are integrated into RE&RI broadly speaking. In addition, observations are made about the working methods and cases currently used in training programmes and materials to provide a closer look at what is being taught, and how.

The findings presented in this deliverable aim to inform the design and adaptation of RE&RI frameworks and training programs that holistically address the environmental and climate dimensions of R&I. These outputs will serve as a cornerstone in the development of practical guidelines (Task 3.2) and tailored training materials (WP4).

This deliverable is structured into two core sections: the first details the review and gap analysis of RE&RI guidelines and frameworks (Task 1.4), and the second outlines the review and gap analysis of existing training materials and programmes (Task 1.3). Within each section, the following information is described:

1. The **research questions and objectives** guiding the analysis.
2. An explanation of the **identification, screening, and assessment methodology** of relevant resources, including the criteria for inclusion and exclusion and the assessment tool used in the analysis.
3. An **overview of the identified resources**, highlighting general trends in how environmental and climate concerns are addressed.
4. The **findings** of the analysis, specifically focusing on references to climate and environmental issues, the relevance and comprehensiveness of the resources, and their applicability and inclusivity for indigenous or disproportionately affected groups; as well as examples of key training resources and their content.

5. **Identification of gaps** in existing guidelines and frameworks (section 2) and training resources (section 3), along with recommendations for improvement, and a discussion of the limitations of this analysis.

2. Review and gap analysis of RE&RI guidelines and frameworks

Methodology

Research question and objectives of the analysis

Achieving the ambitious goals of the European Green Deal requires the full alignment of R&I with relevant environmental and climate challenges, considerations, technologies and ethical principles. To drive this alignment, robust RE&RI frameworks that explicitly address these concerns are essential. These frameworks serve as the foundation for ensuring that R&I contributes positively to the Green Transition while safeguarding public trust and fostering ethical accountability in scientific progress. The RE4GREEN project recognises that existing RE&RI guidelines are widely used by those involved in research. These include EU and internationally recognised documents like the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (ECOC), the Heidelberg Agreement on Environmental Sustainability in Research Funding, and the Nagoya Protocol as well as regional and national documents. While they often provide valuable baseline principles, their applicability to complex environmental and climate challenges is not yet fully understood. This deliverable aims to systematically map these guidelines and frameworks and analyse how well they support the Green Transition. By examining their relevance to environmental and climate concerns in R&I and their comprehensiveness in addressing such concerns, this analysis will identify areas requiring enhancement or new guidelines. The findings will directly contribute to the development of operational ethics and integrity guidelines under Task 3.2. The following research question and objectives guide this analysis:

Research question: How well do existing RE&RI frameworks and guidelines address environmental and climate concerns in the context of R&I, and what gaps need to be addressed?

Objectives:

1. Compile a detailed list of frameworks and guidelines that address environmental and climate concerns in the context of research ethics and integrity.
2. Assess the relevance and comprehensiveness of these guidelines and frameworks with regard to climate or environmental concerns in R&I, using clearly defined criteria that align with the goals of the RE4GREEN project.
3. Identify where these frameworks fall short in addressing environmental and climate ethics and recommend areas for improvement or the creation of new guidelines.

Approach to identifying frameworks and guidelines

To achieve the first objective, the process of identifying relevant RE&RI frameworks and guidelines was structured to ensure the inclusion of documents widely used by stakeholders in research at the international European, national, regional, and institutional levels. We thus followed an iterative process in identifying relevant guidelines and frameworks which included research from past projects, targeted reviews, and independent inquiries of R&I experts in Europe.

The identification process began with a review of existing resources and findings from prior EU-funded projects and initiatives. These included the European Commission's Ethics and Integrity Results Pack (European Commission, 2024), the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (ECOC; ALLEA, 2023) and the Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI by the High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence (HLEG-AI; European Commission, 2019) as well as findings from previously funded EU projects such as TechEthos, iRECS, HYBRIDA, PREPARED, PRINTEGER, SIENNA, and TRUST.

Krishma Labib of RE4GREEN partner AUMC, who was conducting a global review of RE, RI, and open science guidelines and frameworks with a focus on their implications for research fairness (Pallise Perello et al., 2024), contributed a list of compiled guidelines for this report. We leveraged the guidelines and frameworks she identified within the European Research Area, including documents at the national level. As part of our collaborative efforts, we supported her research by helping to identify and engage experts in countries where relevant resources were challenging to locate. These countries included Andorra, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Georgia, Greece, Iceland, Italy, Liechtenstein, Luxembourg, Monaco, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Moldova, Russia, Serbia, Slovenia, Turkey, and Ukraine. Furthermore, we shared our final dataset with Ms Labib to contribute to the robustness of her research and to foster cross-research synergies.

We also drew upon the extensive experience of the RE4GREEN consortium and its Stakeholder Advisory Board (SAB) by inquiring about the RE&RI guidelines and frameworks they use in their day-to-day activities. This ensured that practical and widely recognised resources from a variety of stakeholder groups, such as research managers and administrators, research ethics committees, and citizen scientists, were included in our analysis. Additionally, we utilised the findings from the systematic literature review identifying key concepts and issues in environmental and climate ethics for R&I (Task 1.1); reviewers labelled several sources as "Research ethics and integrity guidelines" within the Covidence platform¹, and we included these in our analysis. Finally, to further ensure the completeness of our dataset, we conducted an independent and targeted search for additional guidelines and frameworks, minimising the risk of omitting critical resources. We used platforms such as Google and The Embassy of Good Science (2022), and search terms included combinations of keywords such as "research ethics guidelines," "research integrity frameworks," "ethics and integrity in research," and "guidelines for responsible innovation."

Screening and inclusion and exclusion criteria

To ensure that the identified RE&RI frameworks and guidelines were relevant and aligned with the research questions and objectives of the analysis, we applied a set of inclusion and exclusion criteria during the screening process. Our inclusion criteria were as follows:

Relevance: The documents must primarily focus on research ethics and integrity.

Geographical scope: The documents must be applicable within the European Research Area (ERA) or recognised by international bodies influencing European research practices. Additionally, global guidelines were considered if they were widely adopted or referenced within the ERA.

Type of document: Grey literature, including RE&RI guidelines, frameworks, codes of conduct, and institutional frameworks (such as those developed by research-performing organisations, funding bodies, or universities),

¹ Covidence is an online tool designed to streamline and manage systematic reviews and is used in Task 1.1 in RE4GREEN, <https://www.covidence.org/>

were included, along with certain relevant research publications. Training materials, tools, and resources (reviewed under Task 1.3) were excluded.

Purpose: Documents needed to provide guidance on ethics and integrity in R&I.

Target audience: Frameworks and guidelines targeting researchers, policymakers, ethics experts and reviewers, citizen scientists, funders, integrity officers, innovators, students, publishers, and editors were included.

Language accessibility: Documents needed to be discoverable through English-language search queries. Once found, non-English documents were considered if they could be translated into English.

Our initial methodology included a time-based inclusion criterion, limiting the selection to guidelines and frameworks published within the last 10 years to capture resources that address contemporary ethical and integrity-relevant considerations in R&I. However, during the analysis phase, we decided to omit this criterion to ensure that no significant or foundational documents were excluded. This adjustment allowed us to include older but still relevant guidelines and frameworks that continue to influence current RE&RI practices such as national ethics codes applicable in Belgium, Hungary, Denmark and Spain among other countries and the OECD Guidelines on Human Biobanks and Genetic Research Databases.

During the initial screening phase, we applied our inclusion and exclusion criteria to filter the documents. We then reviewed each document selected for analysis and searched for relevant keywords (e.g., sustainability, environment, climate, the precautionary principle, carbon neutrality, environmental and/or climate ethics, environmental and/or climate impact, the Green Transition, environmental and/or climate responsibility, the do no significant harm principle, the European Green Deal, net zero), extracting text that referenced environmental or climate concerns. Documents containing relevant references to environmental or climate concerns were then evaluated in detail using the assessment criteria outlined in the following section.

Assessment criteria and alignment with Task 1.1 and Task 1.2 findings

To evaluate the selected RE&RI frameworks and guidelines, we developed a set of assessment criteria to ensure a systematic evaluation of each framework's relevance and comprehensiveness in addressing environmental and climate concerns within R&I. First, we assessed the relevance of the guidelines and frameworks to environmental and climate aspects. To assess relevance, we conducted a detailed review of each document and identified the main issues related to climate or environment that are being addressed in the document. Next, we evaluated the comprehensiveness of each guideline and framework in addressing these relevant aspects. Using a broad range of environmental and climate dimensions identified in Tasks 1.1 and 1.2, we assigned a comprehensiveness level—categorised as low, moderate, or comprehensive—to each guideline and framework. The dimensions identified in Tasks 1.1 and 1.2 included specific ethical or theoretical concepts; principles; domains of technology, research, and innovation; and environmental issues.

Overview of reviewed frameworks and guidelines

The review of RE&RI frameworks and guidelines encompassed a diverse range of documents, varying in geographic focus, authoring organisations, publication or revision dates, disciplinary fields, and target stakeholder groups. The goal of this review was to capture a holistic understanding of the current landscape of RE&RI frameworks and their relevance to environmental and climate concerns. This section provides an aggregated overview of the key characteristics of the reviewed documents.

Through our search methods, we identified 249 resources, including RE and RI guidelines, frameworks, and codes of conduct as well as other types of documents such as practical and operational recommendations,

governance principles, agreements, policy statements, best practices, directives, guidance notes, reports and procedures, among others. The collected resources were published from 1946 to 2024 and encompass various countries and geographical regions, including Albania, Australia, Austria, Belgium, Brazil, Canada, Croatia, Cyprus, Czechia, Denmark, Estonia, the European Union, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, India, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lebanon, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Montenegro, Netherlands, North Macedonia, Norway, Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) countries, Poland, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, UK, Ukraine, the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE) region, and the United States.

Figure 1: Countries in the ERA where we identified guidelines and frameworks.

The resources also covered diverse disciplines, such as AI, biometrics, geolocation, the Internet of Things (IoT), social networks, marketing, security and cybersecurity, anthropology, astronomy, bioethics, biology, biomedical research, biomedicine, carbon dioxide removal, city climate leadership, climate engineering, climate-related financial disclosures, conservation of nature, ecology, engineering, informatics, environmental and resource economics, genome editing in humans, genome-edited crops, geoengineering, health, health databases and biobanks, health science, natural science, health-related research involving humans, environmental research, human biobanks and genetic research databases, humanities and social sciences, inclusivity, innovation, neurotechnology, open and interoperable spatial computing technology, open science, pharmaceuticals, political sciences, and psychology, among others.

Furthermore, the resources are targeted toward various stakeholder groups, and the detailed review process enabled us to identify these groups with greater granularity. This allowed us to highlight specific roles such as AI professionals, businesses, citizen scientists, research performing institutions and organisations, editors and publishers, engineers, ethics experts and reviewers, funders, RE committees, healthcare professionals and

scientific organisations, innovators, integrity officers, pharmaceutical manufacturers and associations, researchers and research managers, local governments, mayors, patients, policymakers, professionals and students.

Assessment and gap analysis of guidelines and frameworks

Developing and using a custom assessment tool

To systematically evaluate how climate and environmental dimensions are integrated into RE&RI frameworks, we developed a custom assessment tool in Microsoft Excel. This matrix was central to organising and conducting our analysis, which unfolded in three key phases: the initial screening, decisions on inclusion or exclusion, and the detailed assessment of selected frameworks. Below, we describe each phase and how the tool supported our process.

Phase 1: Initial screening and metadata collection

The first phase involved screening a wide range of resources to create a comprehensive dataset for evaluation. For each document, we recorded key metadata in the matrix to ensure all relevant information was captured in a consistent and structured way. By systematically gathering this information, we captured the general scope and context of each resource. This information included the following:

- The document's title, source, and author(s)
- Its focus on RE, RI, or both
- The year it was published or last revised
- The type of document
- The geographical area and disciplines it covered
- The intended audience and the language of the document
- A link to the document for reference.

Initial Screening											
	Document Title	Source	RE and/or RI	author(s)	revision	Document Type	of applicability	covered	Targeted audience	Language	Link

Figure 2: Phase 1 in the assessment tool.

Phase 2: Application of inclusion and exclusion criteria

Once the metadata was compiled, we applied our inclusion and exclusion criteria to filter the resources. This step was documented in the matrix using two specific columns: one to indicate whether a document was included or excluded and another to record the justification for each decision. Out of the 249 resources initially screened, 36 were excluded at this stage, leaving 213 for further analysis. The exclusions were primarily based on two key reasons: either the documents were not relevant to the European Research Area (ERA) context, or they did not primarily focus on RE&RI.

Figure 3: Phase 2 in the assessment tool.

The complete dataset of 213 guidelines and frameworks that were included in the detailed assessment process, along with their associated metadata, has been uploaded to the project's open-access repository on Zenodo.²

Phase 3: Detailed assessment

The final phase involved a detailed evaluation of the selected 213 resources to explore how thoroughly they addressed climate and environmental concerns. First, we examined whether each resource included any references to climate or environmental concerns, such as environmental and climate protection or sustainability imperatives. **Out of the 213 resources, 123 made no such references, underscoring a significant lack of integration of these dimensions into existing guidelines and frameworks.**

For the remaining 90 resources that did reference climate or environmental concerns, we conducted a detailed assessment based on the preliminary criteria identified within the literature review of key concepts and issues in environmental and climate ethics for R&I (Task 1.1) and the analysis of research ethics and integrity challenges of technologies and policies supporting the Green Transition (Task 1.2). These criteria were captured in additional columns in the matrix and included the following:

- The relevance and context of the references to environmental or climate concerns.
- Ethical or theoretical concepts mentioned (e.g., sustainability, justice).
- Principles discussed (e.g., precautionary principle, polluter-pays principle).
- Specific domains of technology or innovation covered.
- Environmental issues addressed (e.g., pollution, biodiversity loss).
- A comprehensiveness score to quantify the extent of integration of these dimensions.
- An overall assessment of the resource's depth and relevance.

Review							
References to environmental and climate concerns/Climate Ethics	Relevance to environmental/climate ethics	Specific ethical or theoretical concepts mentioned	Specific principles mentioned	Domains of technology/research/innovation mentioned	Environmental issues mentioned	Comprehensiveness (quantifying box R-U)	Overall Assessment

Figure 4: Phase 3 in the assessment tool.

² <https://zenodo.org/records/14609149>

Figure 5: The process of collecting, screening and assessing RE&RI guidelines and frameworks.

References and relevance to environmental and climate concerns

We began our analysis by investigating how references to climate and environmental concerns in RE&RI guidelines and frameworks have evolved over time. To explore this, we first plotted the number of identified guidelines and frameworks that referenced these concerns against their year of publication or most recent revision. The results of this analysis are presented in *Figure 6* and allow us to draw two significant conclusions based on the production and revision activity of guidelines and frameworks during key periods.

First, a modest increase in the number of relevant guidelines and frameworks is evident after 2009, coinciding with a growing global recognition of climate change as an urgent ethical and systemic issue. This period aligns with pivotal events such as the 2010 Cancun Agreements (COP16; UNFCCC, n.d.), which underscored global commitments to limiting temperature increases and reducing emissions. The rise also reflects the heightened awareness generated by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) reports (IPCC, n.d.) and the early sustainability goals set by initiatives like the EU's 20-20-20 targets (adopted in 2008).

Second, a more pronounced and sustained increase occurs after 2016, which aligns with the adoption of the Paris Agreement (UNFCCC, 2016) and the 2015 United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs; United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs, n.d.), particularly SDG 13 on Climate Action. These milestones established climate ethics as a global priority, influencing policies and ethical considerations across R&I in the ERA. Additional contributing factors include the EU Horizon 2020 program (2014–2020; European Commission, n.d.), which emphasised sustainability and climate action, and societal movements such as the Global Climate Strikes and Fridays for Future (2023), which brought climate concerns to the forefront. This upward trend highlights a positive observation: **RE&RI guidelines and frameworks appear to be responsive to global and European developments.**

Figure 6: Number of guidelines and frameworks addressing climate or environmental concerns over the years.

While the graph offers useful insights, it is important to recognise some limitations. The observed trends are influenced by the availability of resources we could locate for each year. For example, in certain years, only a small number of guidelines or frameworks were found, which may not reflect the actual production of such resources during those periods. Additionally, the apparent decrease in resources after 2021 is more likely due to the limitations in the resources we were able to find rather than an actual decline in the creation of RE&RI guidelines and frameworks. In other words, the graph reflects the number of resources we identified each year, not necessarily the total number of RE&RI guidelines and frameworks that were produced or revised in that year.

To address the limitations of the initial analysis, which relied heavily on annual data, we repeated the process by grouping the guidelines and frameworks into five-year intervals. This method, often referred to as binning or interval aggregation, reduces the variability caused by uneven resource identification and provides a clearer representation of overall trends. The results of this aggregated analysis reveal **a steady upward trend in the integration of climate and environmental concerns into RE&RI frameworks over the past two decades**, which can be observed in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Number of guidelines and frameworks addressing climate or environmental concerns over the years (5-year intervals).

Following the identification of 90 guidelines and frameworks that contained at least some reference to climate or environmental aspects, we conducted a more detailed review to assess their relevance to these issues. Different disciplines (e.g., agricultural sciences, engineering, or medicine) encounter unique issues or challenges that shape their understanding and approach to environmental and climate ethics. Their starting points for environmental and climate ethical issues are naturally very heterogeneous. To ensure consistency in this phase, we developed a systematic approach by identifying a set of key themes commonly addressed within these documents. These themes represented critical dimensions of climate and environmental concerns and were derived through an analysis of the language and concepts present in the guidelines. The key themes identified were as follows:

- Sustainability
- Environment, ecosystem, and biodiversity protection
- Climate change, adaptation, and mitigation
- Resource use, waste, and management
- Pollution, emissions, and environmental footprint
- Environmental and climate harm, risk, and risk assessment
- Environmental responsibility and citizen participation

Sustainability: This theme focused on the integration of sustainability principles into R&I practices, emphasising the importance of aligning with global goals for sustainable development.

Example: "A key focus of the Heidelberg Agreement is to ensure that research funders take a proactive approach to promoting sustainability in scientific research. It calls for funders to set ambitious sustainability goals; share principles for approaching sustainability in research funding based on innovation, experimentation, partnership, diversity and co-creation; highlight the importance of sustainability in their schemes; and support the development and adoption of tools that help researchers to integrate sustainability."

– Introduction to the Heidelberg Agreement on Environmental Sustainability in Research Funding (Weber et al., 2024)

Example: "More rapid exchange of knowledge through open science creates an opportunity to find solutions to international challenges and to share best practices for sustainable development."

– The Research Council Policy for Open Science (Research Council of Norway, 2020)

Environment, ecosystem, and biodiversity protection: This theme addressed the preservation of natural habitats, conservation of biodiversity, and protection of ecosystems. It emphasised the ethical responsibility to safeguard the well-being of all living organisms and the interconnected systems that support life on Earth.

Example: "Especially relevant to genome editing is the principle of protection future generations as well as the protection of the environment, the biosphere, and biodiversity."

– Genome editing in humans: A survey of law, regulation and governance principles (Nordberg & Antunes, 2022)

Example: "...Recognizing the importance of genetic resources to food security, public health, biodiversity conservation, and the mitigation of and adaptation to climate change..."

– Nagoya Protocol on Access to Genetic Resources and the Fair and Equitable Sharing of Benefits Arising from their Utilization to the Convention on Biological Diversity (Convention on Biological Diversity, 2014)

Example: "AI systems should contribute to, and not harm, individual, social and environmental wellbeing...Environmental well-being refers to the well-functioning of ecosystems, sustainability, and the minimization of environmental degradation"

– Ethics By Design and Ethics of Use Approaches for Artificial Intelligence (Dainow & Brey, 2021)

Climate change, adaptation, and mitigation: This theme related to the challenges posed by climate change, including the need for proactive measures to adapt to changing environmental conditions and implement mitigation strategies.

Example: "Medical publishing contributes to carbon emissions that exacerbate climate change, which is an urgent threat to human well-being and planetary health."

– International Committee of Medical Journal Editors Publication Recommendations (ICMJE, 2024)

Example: "...Recognizing the importance of genetic resources to food security, public health, biodiversity conservation, and the mitigation of and adaptation to climate change..."

– Nagoya Protocol on Access to Genetic Resources and the Fair and Equitable Sharing of Benefits Arising from their Utilization to the Convention on Biological Diversity (Convention on Biological Diversity, 2014)

Example: "...Recognizing the importance of genetic resources to food security, public health, biodiversity conservation, and the mitigation of and adaptation to climate change..."

– Nagoya Protocol on Access to Genetic Resources and the Fair and Equitable Sharing of Benefits Arising from their Utilization to the Convention on Biological Diversity (Convention on Biological Diversity, 2014)

Resource use, waste, and management: This theme highlighted the importance of efficient and responsible resource use, focusing on reducing waste, promoting recycling and reuse, and advancing circular economy principles. It also encompassed efforts to minimise the environmental impacts of resource extraction and disposal.

Example: "... researchers should seek to minimize impacts on living subjects of research and on the natural environment and should be aware of the need to manage resources efficiently and sustainably."

– United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) Recommendation on Science and Scientific Researchers (UNESCO, 2018)

Example: "These rules refer to the highest respect of human beings and animals, responsible resource allocation and preservation of the environment."

– Code of Conduct for Healthcare Professionals and Scientific Organizations (Biomedical Alliance in Europe, 2024)

Example: "Failing to follow good research practices violates professional responsibilities. It damages the research processes, degrades relationships among researchers, undermines trust in and the credibility of research, wastes resources, and may expose research participants and subjects, users, society, or the environment to unnecessary harm."

– European Code of Conduct on Research Integrity (ALLEA, 2023)

Pollution, emissions, and environmental footprint: This theme is related to reducing pollution and emissions across various environmental domains, such as air, water, and soil.

Example: "[A researcher should strive] to reduce the climate and environmental footprint of his/her activities..."

– Code of Ethics for Researchers (Czech Academy of Sciences, 2024)

Example: "[Researchers should] take responsibility to search for technological solutions that lower the production of environmentally harmful wastes and lessen environmental pollution"

– Research Ethics Policy (University of Twente, 2019)

Environmental and climate harm, risk, and risk assessment: This theme covered the identification and mitigation of environmental risks, emphasising the importance of precautionary measures and risk assessments to prevent harm. It highlighted the need for ethical consideration of potential environmental consequences and the vulnerabilities of ecosystems and communities.

Example: "All research in natural and engineering sciences should be preceded by an analysis of the associated risks and the impact that the research results may have on society and the environment."

– Code of Ethics for Researchers (Polish Academy of Sciences, 2020)

Example: "...intergenerational justice must go hand in hand with the precautionary principle: do not apply a technology until it is scientifically validated and ethically acceptable...Any research with the potential to impact future generations must be subject to additional rigorous oversight mechanisms. The fundamental aim of this oversight is to safeguard individual and public health and safety, the environment, agriculture and national security for the benefit of present and future generations."

– Report of the International Bioethics Committee (IBC) on the principle of protecting future generations (UNESCO, 2021)

Example: Art 11: "Medical research should be designed and conducted in a manner that avoids or minimizes harm to the environment and strives for environmental sustainability."

– WMA Declaration of Helsinki – Ethical principles for medical research involving human subjects (World Medical Association, 2013)

Environmental responsibility and citizen participation: This theme focused on the role of individuals, communities, and institutions in addressing environmental challenges. It emphasised collective responsibility, equitable benefit sharing, the importance of engaging stakeholders in decision-making processes and considering the effects on future generations.

Example: "Responsibility means, among other things, acknowledging the fact that a researcher does not operate in isolation and hence takes into consideration – within reasonable limits – the legitimate interests of human and animal test subjects, as well as those of commissioning parties, funding bodies, and the environment."

– Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (Dutch Research Council, 2018)

Example: "Responsibility means that the researcher...avoids harming people, society and nature...respects life and maintains a careful attitude to the environment, biosphere and biodiversity."

– Estonian Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (Centre for Ethics, University of Tartu, 2017)

Example: "Recognizing that public awareness of the economic value of ecosystems and biodiversity and the fair and equitable sharing of this economic value with the custodians of biodiversity are key incentives for the conservation of biological diversity and the sustainable use of its components."

– Nagoya Protocol on Access to Genetic Resources and the Fair and Equitable Sharing of Benefits Arising from their Utilization to the Convention on Biological Diversity (Convention on Biological Diversity, 2014)

Example: "Citizen science projects have a genuine scientific outcome, such as answering a research question or informing conservation actions, management decisions, or environmental policy."

– Ten principles of citizen science (ECSA, 2021)

We then analysed and graphed the proportion of the 213 included guidelines and frameworks that addressed each of the identified key themes. As illustrated in Figure 8, **only a subset of the guidelines and frameworks engaged with these relevant themes, highlighting significant gaps in their coverage.** Moreover, even among those that did address these themes, **engagement with climate or environmental ethics within these guidelines and frameworks was often superficial and lacked depth or actionable guidance,** meaning references were typically limited to high-level statements or generic mentions without specific, actionable recommendations for implementation. For example, many documents referred to sustainability or environmental responsibility but failed to provide detailed steps or tools for integrating these concepts into research practices, such as conducting environmental impact assessments or applying the precautionary principle in specific contexts. This pattern was consistent across the dataset, with EU and international guidelines sometimes referencing abstract principles designed for broad applicability, such as *sustainability*, the *precautionary principle* and *intergenerational justice* but lacking context-specific implementation strategies. National and institutional guidelines were more likely to include more tailored recommendations, reflecting the needs of their specific audiences. For example, institutional documents sometimes addressed practical aspects, such as resource conservation or reducing the environmental footprint of research activities. However, even at this level, actionable guidance was limited, and the integration of environmental and climate ethics into broader research ethics frameworks was inconsistent. Overall, the analysis highlights a **gap in the translation of high-level principles into practical strategies and tools for addressing environmental and climate concerns in R&I.** The comprehensiveness of the reviewed guidelines and frameworks will be examined in greater detail in the following subsection.

Figure 8: Proportion of guidelines and frameworks addressing relevant key themes.

Comprehensiveness of relevant resources

The comprehensiveness of the reviewed RE&RI frameworks and guidelines was assessed to determine the extent to which they address environmental and climate concerns in R&I. This analysis considered the breadth and depth of the issues covered by systematically documenting the extent to which they addressed the considerations identified in Tasks 1.1 and 1.2 in the context of climate or environment. These considerations, as previously outlined, included specific ethical or theoretical concepts, principles, domains of technology or research, and environmental issues. The full list of these aspects included:

Table 2: Full list of relevant aspects identified in Tasks 1.1 and 1.2

Specific ethical or theoretical concepts mentioned	Systemic risk, environmental risk, sustainability, strong sustainability, ecomodernism, ecofeminism, responsible research and innovation, responsible innovation, distributive justice, harm-avoidance justice, epistemic justice, participatory justice, recognition justice, intergenerational justice, gender justice, non-ideal justice, energy justice, just transition, utilitarianism, virtue ethics, deontological theory (rights-based approaches), non-anthropocentrism, pragmatism.
Specific principles mentioned	precautionary principle, all-affected principle, do no significant harm principle, no harm principle, leave no one behind principle, polluter-pays principle, beneficiary-pays principle, ability to pay principle, compensation and/or rectification principle, beneficence, solidarity, responsibility, integrity, autonomy and respect for persons, respect for nature and/or the environment, informed consent.
Domains of technology, research, and innovation mentioned	Geoengineering and climate engineering technologies (solar radiation management and/or carbon dioxide removal or negative emissions technologies), digital technologies (ICTs, IoTs, etc.), transportation technologies (self-driving cars, etc), agricultural technologies (climate-smart agricultural technologies, genetically modified organisms), energy technologies (renewables, nuclear, carbon capture and storage, etc.), biotechnologies, nanotechnologies, gene editing technologies, technologies encouraging behavioural change.
Environmental issues mentioned	Climate change, biodiversity loss, pollution, waste, ozone depletion.

During our review, we identified additional considerations beyond those highlighted in Tasks 1.1 and 1.2, including previously unaddressed technologies, research domains, and environmental issues, which were also integrated into our analysis.

Using this structured approach, we analysed which considerations were addressed frequently, which were mentioned less often, and which were entirely absent. **This analysis revealed several areas that remain unaddressed, highlighting gaps in the integration of these considerations into current RE&RI guidelines and frameworks.** To visualise the prevalence of these references, we produced word clouds for each category. These visualisations, presented in Figure 9 - Figure 12, provide an overview of the frequency and prominence of these considerations across the reviewed guidelines and frameworks.

Ethical and theoretical concepts

Figure 9: Word cloud of specific ethical or theoretical concepts mentioned in the reviewed guidelines and frameworks.

In terms of ethical and theoretical approaches, references to sustainability were the most frequent, highlighting its central role in discussions of climate and environmental ethics. Additionally, references to Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) in the context of climate and environment were also prevalent. Other recurring concepts included intergenerational and distributive justice, emphasising the ethical responsibility to ensure fairness across generations and equitable resource distribution. For example, the Best Practice Guide for Research Integrity and Ethics of the Austrian Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research (2020) states that "researchers must above all determine if the planned project involves any aspects that are ethically and/or legally relevant, such as negative consequences for participants and test subjects, animals, the animate and inanimate environment, society, or *future generations*", and guidelines of the National Research Ethics Committees of Norway (2019) state that "research should help counteract global injustice." However, many important considerations, such as energy justice, participatory justice, and epistemic justice, were mentioned far less frequently, indicating gaps in the broader integration of justice-related concepts.

Other concepts identified in the literature review identifying key concepts and issues in environmental and climate ethics for R&I (Task 1.1) were notably absent in the reviewed guidelines and frameworks. These include the following:

- **Ecomodernism:** A perspective that seeks to reconcile technological innovation with environmental sustainability.
- **Ecofeminism:** An approach that links gender justice with environmental ethics.
- **Non-ideal justice:** A framework that focuses on addressing ethical challenges under real-world conditions and imperfect compliance.
- **Virtue ethics:** An ethical framework emphasising the development of moral character and virtues.

- **Pragmatism:** A philosophy that emphasises practical solutions and actionable steps to inform climate and/or environmental action.

Specific principles

Figure 10: Word cloud of specific principles mentioned in the reviewed guidelines and frameworks.

The most frequently mentioned principles were **responsibility, integrity, and respect for nature and the environment**, underscoring the foundational ethical implications of these principles. References to respect for nature and the environment often mirrored language from the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, which advocates researchers to "respect for colleagues, research participants, research subjects, society, ecosystems, cultural heritage, and the environment" (ALLEA, 2023). Informed consent and autonomy were also prominent, reflecting established norms in research ethics, though these principles were most often discussed separately from content specifically addressing environmental and/or climate concerns. In addition, **principles specifically tailored to environmental challenges, such as the precautionary principle and the polluter-pays principle, were referenced much less often.** This discrepancy suggests a need to better integrate principles that address the unique ethical dimensions of climate and environmental issues. Solidarity and beneficence also emerged as recurring themes, though their contextual application to environmental challenges remains limited.

The following principles were notably absent:

- **All-affected principle:** A principle that emphasises the inclusion of all stakeholders impacted by a decision in the decision-making process, focusing on fairness and representation.
- **Do No Significant Harm principle:** A principle that explicitly promotes environmental stewardship by ensuring actions do not cause significant damage to ecosystems or undermine sustainability efforts.
- **Beneficiary-pays principle:** A principle that complements the polluter-pays approach by focusing on those who benefit from environmental exploitation and their responsibility to contribute to mitigation efforts.
- **Ability-to-pay principle:** A principle that addresses equity in climate action by advocating for contributions based on an individual's or group's financial capacity to support environmental solutions.

Domains of technology and research

Figure 11: Word cloud of specific domains of technology and research mentioned in the reviewed guidelines and frameworks.

Biotechnology and information and communication technologies (ICTs) were the most frequently mentioned domains, reflecting their prominence in contemporary R&I. Other emerging fields, such as artificial intelligence, nanotechnology, and robotics, were also referenced, but with varying degrees of detail and emphasis. Notably, domains directly linked to environmental concerns, such as renewable energy technologies and environmental monitoring, appeared less frequently, **suggesting a gap in the prioritisation of technologies that directly address climate and environmental challenges.** References to geoengineering and climate adaptation technologies were also sparse, highlighting a need for more robust ethical guidance in these rapidly advancing fields.

The following technologies and domains of research were not addressed at all in the guidelines and frameworks:

- **Transportation technologies:** Emerging innovations, such as self-driving cars, that have the potential to transform mobility and significantly impact the environment.
- **Technologies encouraging behavioural change:** Tools and innovations aimed at influencing individual and collective behaviours to promote sustainability and reduce environmental impact.

Environmental issues

Figure 12: Word cloud of specific environmental issues mentioned in the reviewed guidelines and frameworks.

A variety of environmental and climate issues were referenced across the guidelines and frameworks. Along the environmental issues identified, biodiversity loss, climate change, and pollution were the most frequently addressed, indicating recognition of these as critical global challenges. However, key concerns such as resource waste and environmental protection were less prominently featured, and issues like ecosystem preservation and biosphere degradation were mentioned infrequently. Topics such as greenhouse gas emissions, ozone layer degradation, and habitat preservation also appeared sporadically, pointing to **uneven attention to some aspects of environmental degradation**. Some issues, such as **reversibility of new technologies** and **societal impacts of environmental policies**, were scarcely mentioned, underscoring areas where further ethical guidance may be needed.

Trends over time

Figure 13: Number of guidelines and frameworks taking into account T1.1 and T1.2 considerations over time (5-year intervals).

We also analysed and graphed the trends over time for the presence of specific ethical or theoretical concepts, principles, technological domains, and environmental issues in the reviewed guidelines and frameworks (Figure 13). The results reveal a gradual increase across all dimensions beginning after 2000, with a more pronounced and rapid rise observed after 2015. This suggests growing recognition and integration of these aspects into research ethics and integrity frameworks over the past two decades.

Comprehensiveness

As a final step of our systematic assessment, we assigned a comprehensiveness score to each of the reviewed guidelines and frameworks to evaluate how thoroughly they addressed climate and environmental concerns. The scoring system categorised frameworks into three levels—Minimal, Moderate, and Comprehensive—based on their engagement with across all four dimensions (ethical concepts, principles, technological domains, and environmental issues). Below, we outline the criteria and characteristics of each level.

Level 1 – Minimal: Frameworks at this level engage with climate and environmental concerns in a superficial manner, often providing only brief mentions without meaningful elaboration. They typically lack coverage of ethical or theoretical concepts, specific principles, and technological domains. Environmental issues, if addressed, are referenced in broad, generic terms without substantive detail.

Level 2 – Moderate: Moderate frameworks show a higher level of engagement, addressing some ethical concepts and principles with moderate specificity. They include limited references to relevant technological

domains and environmental issues, offering more detail than minimal frameworks but still lacking comprehensiveness across all dimensions.

Level 3 – Comprehensive: Comprehensive frameworks provide engagement with climate and environmental concerns. They address a range of ethical concepts, specific principles, technological domains, and environmental issues. These frameworks demonstrate a high level of integration and provide actionable guidance on addressing climate and environmental challenges in research and innovation.

As shown in Figure 14, approximately **58% of the reviewed guidelines and frameworks made no reference to climate or environmental concerns**. Of the remaining, **22% were minimally comprehensive, 14% demonstrated moderate comprehensiveness, and only about 6% were classified as fully comprehensive in addressing these issues.**

Guideline/Framework Distribution by Comprehensiveness

Figure 14: Guidelines and frameworks distribution by comprehensiveness.

Applicability and inclusivity of guidelines and frameworks

Our analysis revealed a **significant gap in the reviewed guidelines and frameworks regarding their applicability to specific stakeholder groups and their inclusivity of disproportionately affected or Indigenous populations in the context of climate and environmental ethics**. As already mentioned, among the resources reviewed, only a subset included references to climate or environmental concerns, and even within this subset, engagement with these issues was largely superficial. This limited focus resulted in a lack of tailored guidance for distinct stakeholder groups, such as policymakers, researchers, or industry practitioners, on how to address climate and environmental ethics effectively.

Furthermore, while some frameworks mentioned disproportionately affected groups, these references were predominantly general and unrelated to climate or environmental concerns. Instead, they tended to focus on broader ethical issues, such as equity and fairness in research practices, without linking these considerations

to the unique challenges posed by climate and environmental issues. Notably, none of the frameworks provided substantive guidance specific to the needs of disproportionately affected or Indigenous populations in the context of climate and environmental ethics. These findings highlight a considerable gap in existing frameworks.

Key areas where RE&RI guidelines and frameworks fall short

The analysis highlights significant shortcomings in their integration of environmental and climate concerns. Despite growing recognition of the importance of these issues, most frameworks fail to address them comprehensively or meaningfully. Key gaps identified include the following:

1. **Minimal mention of environmental and climate concerns:** A striking observation is that about 60% of the frameworks and guidelines reviewed do not reference environmental or climate concerns at all. Among those that do, only around 5% demonstrated comprehensive coverage of these issues. The remaining 35% provided superficial engagement, offering vague or general mentions without actionable guidance or detailed integration. This lack of explicit focus undermines their utility in addressing the pressing challenges posed by the Green Transition.
2. **Superficial engagement with key themes:** Even within frameworks that acknowledge environmental issues, the engagement tends to be shallow. References to critical themes such as sustainability, biodiversity loss, climate change mitigation, and pollution are often limited to high-level statements without practical recommendations or strategies. Broader-scope guidelines, such as those at the EU or international level, occasionally, if at all, reference broad principles like the precautionary principle or sustainability but do not provide concrete implementation guidance. National and institutional-level documents sometimes address more practical aspects, such as resource conservation or reducing the environmental footprint of research activities, yet these mentions remain superficial as well. As a result, stakeholders are often left without clear, actionable ethical frameworks to effectively navigate these challenges.
3. **Neglect of emerging domains:** Frameworks largely fail to address interdisciplinary domains or emerging technologies with significant environmental implications. Solar radiation modification (SRM), geoengineering, renewable energy technologies, and digital tools for promoting sustainable behaviour change are notable examples. Ethical considerations for these fields are urgently needed, given their potential to drive—or hinder—progress toward environmental goals.
4. **Lack of focus on justice-oriented approaches:** Justice-related concepts such as energy justice, participatory justice, and intergenerational justice receive little attention across the reviewed frameworks. This oversight is critical, as these concepts are central to ensuring equitable outcomes for all stakeholders, particularly communities disproportionately affected by environmental degradation and climate change.
5. **Lack of focus on Indigenous populations and disproportionately affected groups:** Despite the ethical imperative to include marginalised groups, one of our high-level observations included the fact that very few frameworks address the specific needs of disproportionately affected or Indigenous populations in the context of environmental and climate concerns. When mentioned, these references are typically generic, failing to provide actionable guidance on protecting these groups' rights or incorporating their perspectives into decision-making processes.

6. **Insufficient integration of sustainability principles:** While sustainability is one of the most frequently mentioned ethical concepts, its treatment is often narrow. Many frameworks fail to incorporate broader sustainability principles, such as circular economy approaches or strategies for minimising environmental footprints in R&I. This limits their relevance to comprehensive environmental stewardship.
7. **Lack of practical and stakeholder-centred guidance:** Frameworks fail to provide tailored, actionable guidance for high-impact stakeholder groups such as policymakers, industry practitioners, researchers, citizens, and communities. While some frameworks superficially reference citizens and communities, they lack depth in addressing their specific roles and needs in environmental and climate ethics. In addition, the complete omission of pragmatism—a philosophy focused on practical, action-oriented solutions—further limits their relevance and usability in addressing real-world challenges.
8. **Limited focus on risk assessment and management:** While some frameworks discuss environmental risks in broad terms, most do not explicitly recommend the use of environmental risk assessments or the implementation of precautionary measures. This limits their ability to effectively promote practices that mitigate potential harm and ensure accountability in R&I activities.
9. **Outdated or static frameworks:** As indicated by the limited references to climate and environmental concerns, many frameworks have not been updated to reflect the evolving landscape of climate and environmental challenges. With rapid advancements in technology and shifting global priorities, static guidelines risk becoming irrelevant or counterproductive. More specifically, only 30 (approximately 14%) out of the 213 guidelines and frameworks we identified were produced or revised in the past two years.

Recommendations for enhanced or new guidelines

To align R&I with the goals of the Green Transition and effectively address climate and environmental challenges, the development of enhanced or entirely new RE&RI guidelines is essential. To support the creation of new, or the enhancement of existing, RE&RI guidelines and frameworks in the context of Task 3.2, we identified the following key areas that highlight emerging needs. These recommendations serve as a starting point and will naturally align with insights from other tasks within RE4GREEN.

1. **Comprehensively integrate environmental and climate dimensions:** New guidelines must explicitly incorporate environmental and climate considerations as central ethical priorities. This includes embedding principles such as the precautionary principle, polluter-pays principle, and do no significant harm principle into the core framework.
2. **Focus on justice and equity:** Enhanced frameworks should prioritise justice-oriented approaches, addressing concepts such as energy justice, intergenerational justice, and participatory justice. These principles ensure fair and equitable outcomes, particularly for marginalised and disproportionately affected populations by environmental degradation and climate change.
3. **Include actionable guidance for stakeholders:** Guidelines need to offer pragmatic, stakeholder-specific strategies that provide actionable steps to implement ethical principles in environmental and climate contexts, ensuring usability and relevance.
4. **Require ethical oversight of emerging technologies:** As technological advancements increasingly intersect with environmental goals, new guidelines must address the unique ethical implications of

emerging domains for sustainability. This oversight is critical to ensuring these technologies contribute positively to the Green Transition.

5. **Holistic sustainability in frameworks:** Future guidelines should go beyond basic sustainability principles to include circular economy practices, resource efficiency, and environmental stewardship across all stages of R&I. These frameworks should offer practical steps for minimising environmental footprints and promoting systemic change.
6. **Encourage meaningful inclusion of the public and local considerations:** New guidelines should actively involve citizens and communities in the decision-making process. This includes emphasising citizen participation, collective responsibility, and equitable benefit-sharing to foster inclusive and locally relevant ethical practices. Furthermore, new guidelines must also account for local contexts and cultural sensitivities, particularly in regions disproportionately affected by climate change.
7. **Emphasise environmental risk management:** Guidelines should highlight the importance of environmental risk assessments and recommend their adoption as a critical component of R&I practices. This approach promotes the proactive identification and mitigation of potential harms, fostering greater accountability and aligning R&I activities with sustainability goals.
8. **Adopt dynamic and adaptive approaches:** Given the rapidly evolving nature of climate challenges and technological advancements, enhanced guidelines should be flexible and adaptive, allowing for updates to address emerging issues and innovations.

Limitations of the analysis

While this analysis provides valuable insights into the state of RE&RI guidelines and frameworks and their integration of environmental and climate dimensions, some limitations must be acknowledged to ensure transparency and contextual understanding:

1. **Limited dataset scope:** Although significant effort was made to identify a wide range of relevant frameworks, the analysis relied heavily on accessible documents in English or those translatable into English. This constraint may have excluded region-specific or non-English guidelines, particularly those from smaller organisations or countries with less global influence in RE&RI. Additionally, the analysis primarily focused on frameworks applicable within the ERA, potentially underrepresenting perspectives and approaches from non-European contexts or regions.
2. **Evolving nature of environmental and climate challenges:** Climate and environmental concerns are rapidly evolving, and the frameworks reviewed may not fully reflect future advancements, challenges, or priorities. This temporal limitation highlights the need for ongoing updates and adaptability in future analyses.
3. **Subjectivity in comprehensiveness scoring:** Despite the use of structured assessment criteria, the evaluation of comprehensiveness inevitably involved subjective judgment which is an inherent characteristic of this type of qualitative analysis. While efforts were made to minimise bias and ensure consistency, the interpretative nature of evaluating diverse and complex frameworks means that individual perspectives are an unavoidable element of the process.
4. **Potential overgeneralisation:** Given the large number of frameworks reviewed, the analysis necessarily aggregated findings to draw overarching conclusions. This approach may obscure some nuances or context-specific strengths and weaknesses within individual frameworks.

By acknowledging these limitations, this analysis aims to provide a transparent and balanced foundation for further exploration and improvement of RE&RI guidelines to better address environmental and climate challenges. Future studies should seek to address these limitations.

3. Review and Gap Analysis of Existing Training Materials/Programmes

Methodology

Research question and objectives of the analysis

Complementary to the need for robust and explicit RE&RI frameworks and guidelines addressing climate and environmental issues, is the need for comprehensive and empowering training materials and programmes. Training and education can guide students, researchers, citizen scientists and ethics reviewers in the proper application of guidelines and frameworks within their professional contexts, as well as inspiring mindset shifts and behavioural changes which facilitate the alignment of daily practices with principles of environmental and climate responsibility and impact reduction. Task 1.3 aims to assess which training programmes and materials currently available within the ERA address environmental and climate ethics in the context of research and innovation, and to what extent they do so, with the ultimate aim of informing the enhancement RE&RI frameworks and developing new training materials.

This research will be guided by the following research question and objectives:

Research question: Within the ERA, how are key environmental and climate ethical concerns relevant to R&I and RE&RI addressed in existing training programmes and materials?

Objectives:

1. Map the training programmes and materials available within the ERA which address climate and environmental concerns in relation to R&I and RE&RI.
2. Identify the gaps in the coverage of these programmes and training materials regarding ethical concepts and perspectives; ethical principles and values; research and innovation domains; and environmental and climate issues.

Approach to identifying training programmes and materials

The search strategy used to identify training programmes and materials was rigorous, comprehensive, and designed to “cast a wide net” to capture any resources potentially relevant to the research question and objectives. The search strategy was implemented in collaboration with the Digital Methods Institute of the Amsterdam Institute for Humanities Research, University of Amsterdam, using two of their tools – the [Lippmannian Device](#) and [Search Engine Scraper](#) . The Search Engine Scraper gathers results for a given search query run using a specific search engine, and outputs a list of web pages the search engine returned for that query. The Lippmannian device, in contrast, batch queries within predefined websites.

Full details of the search strategy (including queries, source websites and parameters used with each tool) are available on Zenodo, here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12721145> and here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14025893>.

The identification process consisted of four steps. First, we searched for relevant programmes and materials on university websites within the ERA. We compiled the list of universities using the Times Higher Education and QS university rankings for 2024 – any university within the ERA from either ranking was included. This approach was taken simply to systematically compile a comprehensive list of universities, rather than to focus on the kinds of universities typically included within these rankings (“elite” universities). This potential bias was offset by the third step in the identification process, described below. We defined a search query to identify educational resources covering the environment, climate and sustainability; research, innovation and technology; and ethics and integrity. Using the Lippmannian Device, we systematically searched for this query within the university websites from our list. Second, we compiled a list of repositories of training materials (such as RRI Tools) and online course databases (such as Coursera.com). We used the same strategy as above to identify materials and courses containing our keywords.

Third, we performed an advanced Google search within each ERA region (Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, etc.) using the Search Engine Scraper. We adjusted our search query to take into account that this search was not delimited to websites containing training resources, but was implemented across the whole of Google, adding search terms such as “course”, “training”, etc. This search element introduced the potential of identifying training programmes and materials from outside of academia, or in less traditional formats such as podcasts or interactive exhibits.

Fourth and lastly, to ensure that this broad, automated search was complemented by well-informed suggestions and that key resources were not overlooked, we consulted all RE4GREEN partners about our task and requested recommendations of suitable training programmes and materials. These resources were gathered on a continual basis until the screening process for systematically gathered resources was complete, then were screened and integrated as a final step before analysis.

This multi-step process resulted in a pool of 16,083 potentially relevant resources (not including partners’ suggestions) which were then screened for relevance against inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Screening, inclusion and exclusion criteria, and data extraction

To select only those training programmes and materials which fell within the scope of the goals of Task 1.3 – to identify gaps in existing resources – for analysis, we developed and applied inclusion and exclusion criteria. Search results were screened against the following criteria:

Table 3: Inclusion and exclusion criteria for training programmes and training materials

Training programmes	Training materials
Inclusion	
Geographical: provided by a university within an ERA country	Geographical: accessible to ERA-based users
Quality:	Quality: Up to date and in line with current scientific and technical understanding
- Provided by a university ranked by THE 15 and QS 16 in 2024	Time frame: published during or since 2015

<p>- Up to date and in line with current scientific and technical understanding</p> <p>Time frame:</p> <p>course provided in academic year 2023/2024</p> <p>Language: must be identifiable using English language search queries. Once identified, non-English content will be translated into English</p> <p>Content:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Must discuss key climate and environmental concerns applicable to either the processes or outputs of R&I, and/or as an RE&RI consideration - Discussion should, at minimum, consist of engagement with these topics either as themes running throughout a programme, or as one defined section of focus within a broader programme 	<p>Language: must be identifiable using English language search queries. Once identified, non-English content will be translated into English</p> <p>Content:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Must discuss key climate and environmental concerns applicable to either the processes or outputs of R&I, and/or as an RE&RI consideration - Discussion should, at minimum, consist of engagement with these topics either as themes running throughout training materials, or as one defined section of focus within broader training materials <p>Access: publicly and freely available (including on websites where a free account is required for access)</p> <p>Content type: text, video, audio (including descriptions of other formats, e.g. exhibitions, workshops, etc.)</p> <p>Target audience: university students, researchers/scientists, citizen scientists, teachers/trainers, ethics reviewers</p>
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Exclusion

<p>Geographical: provided by a university outside the ERA</p> <p>Quality:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provided by a university other than those ranked by THE 15 and QS 16 in 2024 - Out of date due to technological advances or developments in scientific understanding <p>Time frame: course provided in the academic year 2022/2023 or earlier</p> <p>Language: no identifying information available in English</p> <p>Content:</p>	<p>Geographical: not accessible to ERA-based users</p> <p>Quality: Out of date due to technological developments or developments in scientific understanding</p> <p>Time frame: Published during or before 2014</p> <p>Language: no identifying information available in English</p> <p>Content:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No relevance for R&I - Discussion of R&I but no relevance for RE&RI or substantial engagement with climate and environmental
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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No relevance for R&I - Discussion of R&I but no relevance for RE&RI or substantial engagement with climate and environmental concerns - Relevant topics discussed from an overwhelmingly management, business, financial, tourism or development perspective 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Relevant topics discussed from an overwhelmingly management, business, financial, tourism or development perspective <p>Access: paywalled content</p> <p>Content type: books, articles (unless used as case studies), theses, blog posts, news items, guidelines, statements or policies</p> <p>Target audience: all categories other than those mentioned in the inclusion criteria</p>
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All resources were thoroughly screened for relevance; 100% of resources were screened by one reviewer, then 15% of resources were screened by a second reviewer. The purpose of double screening was, firstly, to catalyse discussion between reviewers to ensure a consistent interpretation and application of the inclusion and exclusion criteria, and, secondly, to empirically assess this by calculating interrater agreement between reviewers. 15% of the resources equated to 2,429 programmes and materials, and the selection of which resources to double screen was random. This sample was sufficient for us to determine that the interrater agreement was high enough (over 75%) to justify screening the majority of resources only once. Double screening 100% of the resources was therefore not considered an efficient use of time and resources. Interrater agreement was 95% for "university" results, 78% for "repository/database" results, and 80% for "regions" results). Disagreements regarding whether to include or exclude a given resource were discussed and resolved in team meetings. The inclusion and exclusion criteria were refined slightly following the interrater comparison between the first and second rounds of screening for the first batch of results (ERA region web searches). These minor amendments concerned adjustments to the timeframe, access and content requirements with the goal of specifying more precisely which results are considered relevant.

Following the screening process, 370 resources in total were found to meet our inclusion criteria. This included 251 training programmes and 119 training materials. Descriptive data was extracted for the included results, and can be found in **appendix C** (programmes) and **appendix D** (materials). This process included categorising the resources as "programmes" or "materials", recording information about the intended audience (programme level), and recording the infrastructure associated with the resource (which university, project, individual, or collective produced or hosts the resource).

Overview of training programmes and materials

The 370 resources identified via the combination of a broad search strategy with rigorous screening were diverse in nature with regard to several aspects.

Regarding resource type, the 251 training programmes that were identified included university programmes of all levels (bachelors, masters, PhD-level courses, adult/lifelong learning, multi-level courses), including novel transdisciplinary specialisations, tracks or certificates, such as the Berlin Ethics Certificate. Non-university training courses were also classified as programmes, as were summer/winter schools, and

lecture/webinar/seminar series hosted by universities. Resources were classified as training materials if it was possible to immediately access and use or save the content, or if a substantial and educational description of a one-off training event was available. This category included 119 podcasts, case studies, workshops, toolkits, games, and example teaching presentations/handouts, amongst others.

Geographically speaking, almost all ERA countries produced at least 1 resource (either a training programme or material) falling within our scope, the exceptions to this being Croatia, Luxembourg, Malta and Portugal. Many resources were also authored by multi-national European collectives, often in the form of inter-university collaborations (e.g. 4.TU Federation) or European projects (e.g. COMPASS, SPARKLE, AGEMERA). Some resources, often non-university courses, were authored by international organisations including The World Bank, the United Nations Institute for Training and Research and the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. Resources from non-ERA countries were included in our analysis if they were publicly and freely available online and accessible from Europe. These resources were developed in non-EU countries including China, India, New Zealand, South Africa, Taiwan, the UK and the USA.

Figure 15: Training resources identified in the ERA

Across the ERA, there was a large variance in the volume of training programmes and materials identified per country. This ranged from the identification of 1 relevant programme (Malta) to 41 programmes and 5 materials (Netherlands). Of these 41 Dutch programmes, Delft University of Technology hosted the most, with

8 programmes and individual modules across bachelors and masters levels, including "Ethics and Impacts of Global Interventions", "Ethics of Technological Risk", "Climate Ethics", "Environmental Ethics" and "The engineer in society".

Figure 16: Training resources distribution across ERA countries

There are four stakeholder groups of particular relevance for the analysis of training resources, these are:

1. Students, early career researchers and senior researchers;
2. Ethics reviewers in various disciplines within higher education institutions;
3. Horizon Europe ethics appraisal scheme experts; and
4. Citizen scientists.

Where it was possible to identify a target group for our included training programmes, the vast majority were designed with students, early career researchers and senior researchers in mind. One workshop (programme) concerns ethics reviewers within higher education institutions – the University of Antwerp Faculty of Business and Economics Research Morning on 'Ethics and Sustainability', and one presentation (material) - explicitly targeted Horizon Europe ethics experts. Two programmes and two materials explicitly addressed citizen science, and covered issues such as data quality, the SDGs, and ethical issues in environmental monitoring.

A central component of the RE4GREEN project is the Social Labs (SLs) (WP2). Using another keyword search methodology, we categorised the included training resources according to their approximate applicability to each SL topic area. For example, the first SL topic area is "Health; Culture and inclusive society; Civil security", so training programmes and materials with content containing the keywords "Health", "Culture", "Inclusive society", "Inclusion", "Inclusive", "Civil security" and "Security" were considered to have some applicability for this area – 58% of resources, in this case. Using this method, we found that 55% of resources relate to the second SL topic area, "Digital; Industry and space"; 59% to the third, "Climate and mobility"; 37% to the fourth,

"Energy"; 36% to the fifth, "Waters; Oceans"; and 71% to the sixth and final SL topic area, "Food, bioeconomy, agriculture, environment; Soil; Natural resources". This approach allows us to align our findings about currently available training resources with insights gained through the SL process regarding, for example, key climate and environmental ethics knowledge that is considered essential for certain stakeholders. We can then capitalize on these synergies in the training development process (WP4) to efficiently repurpose relevant pre-existing materials, and target important gaps in the creation of new materials.

Assessment and gap analysis of training programmes and materials

Approach to content analysis

Due to the nature of some of our target training resources - particularly university modules, courses and programmes, for which it is not common practice to share educational content on public university webpages - data available for analysis reflected the descriptions of the content available online, and not full descriptions such as programme curricula which might be available elsewhere. Therefore, the content that was included in the analysis includes both actual training content, as well as descriptions of content that was not directly accessible.

The content analysis process was carried out in collaboration with the Digital Methods Initiative of the University of Amsterdam. Content was gathered automatically via web scraping and saved in text format. This text was added to the data extraction tables produced from the screening process, in this way creating a combined dataset of both the metadata associated with each training programme or material and the available content. This comprehensive overview of each training resource served as the dataset within which we performed a more granular keyword search.

We defined sets of keywords based on our objectives to **map the included training resources addressing climate and environmental concerns in relation to R&I and RE&RI (objective 1)**, and to **identify the gaps in their coverage of ethical concepts and perspectives; ethical principles and values; research and innovation domains; and environmental and climate issues (objective 2)**.

To address **objective 1**, we repurposed the original search terms used to identify potentially relevant training resources to cluster included programmes and materials according to whether their content referred to (1) the environment and/or climate; (2) R&I in general; and (3) RE&RI more specifically. The keywords used for each cluster were:

Environment/climate: "Sustainable", "Sustainability", "Climate", "Environment", "Environmental", "Green"

R&I: "Research", "Science", "Technology", "Technologies", "Innovation", "Innovations"

RE&RI: "Research Integrity", "Research Ethics", "Responsible Conduct of Research", "RCR", "Responsible Research and Innovation", "RRI"

To identify environmental ethics and climate ethics resources specifically, we included a cluster made up of "Environmental Ethics" and "Climate Ethics".

The presence or absence of any keyword from a given cluster indicated whether each programme or material should be counted within that cluster. The frequency and proportion of overlapping resources was then calculated for all cluster combinations to build a conceptual map of the training resources.

To address **objective 2**, we converted the framework of key issues identified via the scoping review and analysis of relevant literature performed in Task 1.1 into a more detailed set of keyword clusters. This allowed for the clustering of included programmes and materials according to whether or not their content addressed at least one (1) ethical concept or perspective; (2) ethical principle or value; (3) research and innovation domain; and (4) environmental or climate issue.

A key aim of the RE4GREEN project is to maintain an awareness of the plurality of environmental values and human-nature relationships that exist globally, and that have implications for R&I practice and RE&RI. To ensure that the concerns of a diversity of communities could be identified using our analysis approach, we supplemented the list of "Ethical concepts and perspectives" keywords with new keywords drawn from the WECF Glossary and REGREEN project proposal. These words are formatted in *italics*.

Within Europe, the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (ALLEA) is a central guiding document for research integrity practice and principles. It provides guidance that "applies to research in all scientific and scholarly fields". To ensure that we identified any references to the four central principles of this document – respect, accountability, reliability and honesty – within the training resources, the list of "Ethical principles and values" was supplemented with 4 additional keywords, formatted in *italics*, underlined.

The lists below show, in quotation marks, the exact keywords used and whether they were grouped by concept to form a sub-category, formatted in **bold**, within the four main keyword clusters. This approach was taken if concepts could be referred to using multiple different terms or abbreviations, or if related concepts could be combined to provide a more informative perspective on our results. The results tables in the following sections report at the level of sub-categories, if these used, rather than each keyword within the sub-category.

Table 4: Ethical concepts and perspectives keywords

Ethical concepts and perspectives	
Sub-category	Keyword
	"Systemic risk"
	"Environmental risk"
	"Risk"
	"Sustainability"
	"Strong sustainability"
	"Responsible innovation"
	"Ecomodernism"
Ecofeminism	"Ecofeminism"
	<i>"Ecofeminist"</i>

Intersectionality	<i>"Intersectional"</i>
	<i>"Intersectionality"</i>
	<i>"Indigenous"</i>
Intercultural approaches	<i>"Intercultural"</i>
	<i>"Local ecological"</i>
	<i>"Traditional ecological"</i>
	<i>"Non-Western"</i>
	<i>"Global South"</i>
	<i>"Global East"</i>
	<i>"Plural"</i>
	<i>"Plurality"</i>
	<i>"Pluralism"</i>
	<i>"Pluralist"</i>
	<i>"Pluralistic"</i>
	"Harm-avoidance justice"
	"Epistemic justice"
	"Participatory justice"
	"Recognition justice"
	"Intergenerational justice"
	"Gender justice"
	"Non-ideal justice"
	"Energy justice"
	"Justice"
	"Just transition"
	"Utilitarianism"

	"Virtue ethics"
	"Deontological theory"
	"Non-anthropocentrism"
	"Citizenship theory"
	"Pragmatism"

Table 5: Ethical principles and values keywords

Ethical principles and values	
Sub-category	Keyword
Precautionary principle	"Precautionary principle"
	"Precautionary"
All-affected principle	"All-affected principle"
	"All-affected"
Do no (significant) harm principle	"Do no significant harm principle"
	"Do no significant harm"
	"No harm principle"
	"No harm"
Leave no one behind principle	"Leave no one behind principle"
	"Leave no one behind"
Polluter-pays principle	"Polluter-pays principle"
	"Polluter-pays"
Beneficiary-pays principle	"Beneficiary-pays principle"
	"Beneficiary-pays"
Ability to pay principle	"Ability to pay principle"
	"Ability to pay"
Compensation principle	"Compensation principle"

	"Compensation"
Rectification principle	"Rectification principle"
	"Rectification"
	"Beneficence"
	"Solidarity"
	"Responsibility"
	"Integrity"
	"Autonomy"
	"Respect for persons"
	"Respect for nature"
	"Respect for the environment"
	<i>"Respect"</i>
	"Informed consent"
	<i>"Accountability"</i>
	<i>"Reliability"</i>
	<i>"Honesty"</i>

Table 6: Research and innovation domains

Research and innovation domains	
Sub-category	Keyword
	"Geoengineering"
	"Climate engineering"
Solar radiation management	"Solar radiation management"
	"SRM"
Carbon dioxide removal	"Carbon dioxide removal"
	"CDR"

Negative emissions technologies	"Negative emissions technologies"
	"NETs"
Digital technologies	"Digital technologies"
	"Digital technology"
Information and communication technologies	"Information and communication"
	"ICT"
	"ICTs"
Internet of Things	"Internet of things"
	"IoT"
	"IoTs"
Artificial intelligence	"Artificial intelligence"
	"AI"
Transportation technologies	"Transportation technologies"
	"Transportation technology"
	"Self-driving cars"
Agricultural technologies	"Agricultural technologies"
	"Agricultural technology"
Climate smart agricultural technologies	"Climate smart agricultural technologies"
	"Climate smart agriculture"
	"CSA"
Genetically modified organisms	"Genetically modified organisms"
	"GMO"
	"GMOs"
Energy technologies	"Energy technologies"
	"Energy technology"
Renewables	"Renewable"

	"Renewables"
	"Nuclear"
Carbon capture and storage	"Carbon capture and storage"
	"CCS"
Biotechnology	"Biotechnologies"
	"Biotechnology"
Nanotechnology	"Nanotechnologies"
	"Nanotechnology"
	"Gene editing"
	"Behaviour change technology"

Table 7: Environmental and climate issues

Environmental and climate issues	
Sub-category	Keyword
	"Climate change"
	"Biodiversity loss"
	"Water pollution"
	"Air pollution"
	"Soil pollution"
	"Pollution"
	"Waste"
	"E-waste"
	"Ozone depletion"
	"Ocean acidification"

Focus on research and innovation generally, or research ethics and integrity specifically

As described in the inclusion criteria, resources were only included if they addressed key climate and environmental concerns applicable to either the processes or outputs of R&I, and/or as an RE&RI consideration. The overlap between the appearance of keywords addressing climate and environmental concerns and keywords addressing R&I or RE&RI within the resources provides an indication of engagement with RE&RI frameworks.

We found 218 **training programmes** (86.9%) that addressed both the environment/climate and research/innovation using the specific keywords that we searched for; and there were 25 programmes (10%) where environment/climate was discussed alongside both research/innovation and research ethics/integrity. "Climate ethics" and/or "Environmental ethics" was specifically mentioned in 37 programmes (14.7%), and with research/innovation in 35 programmes (13.9%), and with research ethics/integrity in 4 programmes (1.6%).

We identified 87 **training materials** (73.1%) that addressed both the environment/climate and research/innovation; and there were 15 materials (12.6%) where environment/climate was discussed alongside both research/innovation and research ethics/integrity. "Climate ethics" and/or "Environmental ethics" was specifically mentioned in 12 materials (10.1%), and was these mentions always co-occurred with research/innovation (12 materials, 10.1%), whereas they only co-occurred with research ethics/integrity in 2 materials (1.7%).

Most resources therefore addressed, to some degree, climate and environmental aspects of research and innovation (305 resources, 82.4%), whereas a small minority (43 resources, 11.6%) showed some engagement with research ethics and integrity frameworks specifically.

Climate ethics

"Addressing the climate problem requires more than just developing and applying a certain technology. It demands considerations of whose interests and whose rights are at stake. It also requires reflection on how and "under which condition" technology can change and shape the world for the better."

– [Dr. Ir. Behnam Taebi](#)

Environmental Ethics

"How we consider the environment can inform how we live our daily lives as individuals, but it also has lasting implications for how technologies and engineering practices intervene in the world."

– [Dr. Andrea Gammon](#)

Figure 17: Quotes from course coordinators of the Climate Ethics and Environmental Ethics masters courses at Delft University of Technology, which cover topics such as the Anthropocene, climate justice, non-human entities and indigenous philosophies, particularly

Ethical Concepts and Perspectives

13 of 28 ethical concepts and perspectives appeared in training materials (Table 8), and 16 of 27 appeared in training programmes (Table 9).

Sustainability Resources most frequently address sustainability specifically, with sustainability appearing in 56.3% of training material descriptions and 64.9% of training programme descriptions. (Table 8 and Table 9)

Risks

Risk was also a frequent concept engaged with, appearing in 18.5% and 18.3% of training material and training programme descriptions respectively. 'Environmental' and 'systemic' risks specifically were infrequently addressed however, with just 0.8% of training materials and training programmes mentioning environmental risk and no materials or programmes mentioning systemic risks. (Table 8 and Table 9)

Justice

Justice was the third most frequent concept, mentioned in 16.8% and 20.3% of training materials and programmes respectively. Specific goals or approaches to justice however referred to infrequently. In the training materials, a just transition and distributive justice were both referred to in just 0.8% of resources. Other theories, types or approaches to justice (intergenerational, non-ideal, recognition, harm-avoidance, gender, energy, epistemic, participatory) were not mentioned at all, perhaps indicating a shallow engagement with justice as a concept. The results for training programmes were similar, with mention of a just transition, intergenerational justice and distributive justice in 2%, 0.8% and 0.8% of programmes respectively. (Table 8 and Table 9)

Inclusion

Concepts related to *who* the resources consider important actors in relation to environmental and sustainability considerations in research and innovation were also quite infrequent across the training materials and programmes. 'Intercultural approaches' were mentioned in 7.6% of materials and 10.8% of programmes, 'indigenous' was mentioned in 5.9% of materials and 3.2% of programmes, 'ecofeminism' was mentioned in 1.7% of training materials and 1.6% of programmes, and intersectionality was referred to in 3.4% of training materials and 2.8% of programmes. (Table 8 and Table 9)

Deontology, utilitarianism, virtue ethics, and pragmatism

Training materials also infrequently mentioned overarching ethical theories. Utilitarianism and virtue ethics were the most frequently mentioned, though still in just 2.5% and 0.8% of training materials respectively and both theories were mentioned in 0.4% of training programmes. Deontology and pragmatism were not mentioned at all in any training material or programme description. (Table 8 and Table 9)

Reflection and Responsibility – Berlin Ethics Certificate is an interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary certification program that allows students to integrate a specialization in ethics, technology reflection and science reflection within their own course of study. The Berlin Ethics Certificate is awarded by the presidium of the TU Berlin. It is a certificate program of the [Berlin University Alliance](#) and coordinated by the [Berlin Ethics Lab](#) at the TU Berlin.

Climate Justice

Societal interventions to mitigate climate change necessarily confront complex ethical issues to do with justice, collective and historical responsibility, or the very conceptualization of nature, the human or time itself. How can a just energy transition be made possible in an age of corporate and imperial power? How should we govern innovation, considering the current drive towards AI is exacerbating energy consumption and environmental issues across the globe? The specialization area Ethics and Climate Justice aims to facilitate ethical reflection on local to planetary-scale action surrounding climate change. Students investigate the possibility of transformative change through integrative methods of critical reflection, inter- and transdisciplinarity, sustainability science and technology assessment.

Animal Ethics

The field of Animal Ethics deals with manifold questions, which concern, for example, experiments on animals, the agricultural use of animals, the keeping of zoo animals, or the keeping of pets. Is it morally justifiable to instrumentalize animals for human welfare, let them suffer or kill them? Under what conditions can such actions be morally justified? What rights do animals have? What grounds can be found for criticizing moral anthropocentrism? In the specialization Animal Ethics, students gain the opportunity to deal with such questions in depth.

Figure 18: The Berlin Ethics Certificate is a training programme offered by the Technical University of Berlin, Germany that engages with sustainability, rights and justice.

ENVIRONMENTAL CHANGE AND GLOBAL SUSTAINABILITY | MASTER'S PROGRAMME

IND-500 Indigenous Studies, 15 cr

Indigenous studies provide an opportunity to foster knowledge of Indigenous societies in local and global approaches. It offers transformative and decolonial methodological and analytical tools to approach different Indigenous social worlds, power relations, and reconciliation. The program introduces students to Indigenous knowledge-production as a relational and interactive process. Engaging with diverse local and land-based learning methods, students became familiar with historical and contemporary perspectives and themes within Indigenous studies.

This minor uniquely covers the following thematic, methodological, and theoretical competencies: Indigenous education and languages; Indigenous research methodologies and ethics; biocultural diversity, Indigenous arts, and Indigenous rights and history.

The indigenous studies module can benefit students planning careers in policy-making, environmental and sustainability sectors, education, law, economy, social work, health care, museums, and various areas of culture.

Figure 19: The Environmental Change and Global Sustainability masters programme offered by the University of Helsinki, Finland engages with indigenous environmental and climate knowledge

Table 8: Appearance of ethical concept or perspective in the training materials

Ethical concept or perspective			
Absent	Present	Addressed in (X) resources	%
Systemic risk	Sustainability	67	56,3
Ecomodernism	Risk	22	18,5
Non-ideal justice	Justice	20	16,8
Intergenerational justice	Intercultural approaches	9	7,6
Recognition justice	Indigenous	7	5,9
Participatory justice	Intersectionality	4	3,4
Citizenship theory	Utilitarianism	3	2,5
Deontological theory	Responsible innovation	2	1,7
Harm-avoidance justice	Ecofeminism	2	1,7
Epistemic justice	Environmental risk	1	0,8
Strong sustainability	Distributive justice	1	0,8
Gender justice	Just transition	1	0,8
Energy justice	Virtue ethics	1	0,8
Non-anthropocentrism			
Pragmatism			

Table 9: Appearance of ethical concept or perspective in the training programmes

Ethical concept or perspective			
Absent	Present	Addressed in (X) programmes	%
Epistemic justice	Sustainability	163	64,9
Gender justice	Justice	51	20,3
Citizenship theory	Risk	46	18,3

Non-ideal justice	Intercultural approaches	27	10,8
Non-anthropocentrism	Responsible innovation	13	5,2
Deontological theory	Indigenous	8	3,2
Energy justice	Intersectionality	7	2,8
Harm-avoidance justice	Just transition	5	2,0
Participatory justice	Ecofeminism	4	1,6
Pragmatism	Intergenerational justice	2	0,8
Systemic risk	Environmental risk	2	0,8
Ecomodernism	Distributive justice	2	0,8
	Strong sustainability	1	0,4
	Recognition justice	1	0,4
	Utilitarianism	1	0,4
	Virtue ethics	1	0,4

Ethical Principles and Values

11 of 22 ethical principles and values appeared in training materials (Table 10), and 11 of 22 appeared in training programmes (Table 11).

RE/RI principles

The most frequent principles mentioned across the resources were those associated most commonly with the responsible conduct of research (Table 10). The principle of responsibility (12.6% of materials and 23.9% of programmes) was the most frequently mentioned across all resources. Additional research integrity principles such as accountability (7.6% of materials and 2.4% of programmes), reliability (1.7% of materials and 5.6% of programmes) and honesty (0.8% of programmes and in no materials) appeared less frequently. Principles more frequently associated with research ethics, such as autonomy (2.5% of materials and 4% of programmes), informed consent (1.7% of materials and 0.8% of programmes) and do no (significant) harm (0.8% of materials and 0.4% of programmes), were also infrequently mentioned across resources, with some very fundamental principles associated with research ethics principles – such as beneficence – absent from resource descriptions.

Environmental ethics principles

Principles more frequently associated with environmental and climate ethics – such as All-affected, Polluter-pays, Beneficiary-pays, Ability to pay, Rectification – were also completely absent from resource descriptions.

Research integrity, Ethics and the Sustainable Development Goals within the context of citizen science (RIECS)

Figure 20: The Research integrity, Ethics and the Sustainable Development Goals within the context of citizen science course provided by the European Citizen Science Academy engages with research ethics and integrity principles

Table 10: Appearance of ethical principle or value in the training materials

Ethical principle or value			
Absent	Present	Addressed in (X) resources	%
Ability to pay principle	Responsibility	15	12,6
Respect for nature	Accountability	9	7,6
Beneficence	Respect	8	6,7
Honesty	Integrity	4	3,4
Beneficiary-pays principle	Solidarity	3	2,5
Rectification principle	Autonomy	3	2,5
Respect for persons	Informed consent	2	1,7

Respect for the environment	Reliability	2	1,7
All-affected principle	Precautionary principle	1	0,8
Leave no one behind principle	Do no (significant) harm principle	1	0,8
Polluter-pays principle	Compensation principle	1	0,8

Table 11: Appearance of ethical principle or value in the training programmes

Ethical principle or value			
Absent	Present	Addressed in (X) programmes	%
Precautionary principle	Responsibility	60	23,9
Polluter-pays principle	Integrity	33	13,1
Respect for nature	Respect	18	7,2
Rectification principle	Reliability	14	5,6
All-affected principle	Autonomy	10	4,0
Beneficiary-pays principle	Accountability	6	2,4
Beneficence	Compensation principle	3	1,2
Respect for persons	Solidarity	2	0,8
Respect for the environment	Informed consent	2	0,8
	Honesty	2	0,8
	Leave no one behind principle	1	0,4
	Do no (significant) harm principle	1	0,4

Research and Innovation Domains

15 of 22 research and innovation domains appeared in training materials (Table 12), and 16 appeared in training programmes (Table 13).

Environmental and natural sciences

The only keywords related to environmental and natural research which appeared in more than 5% of resources were 'renewables' (10.9% of materials and 10.4% of programmes), biotechnology (7.6 % of materials and 11.6% of programmes), and climate engineering (6.7% of materials but just 0.4% of programmes).

Computational science and methods

Apart from Artificial Intelligence (AI), which was referenced in 14.3% of training materials and 29.5% of programmes, other computational resource use was addressed infrequently apart, with terms including ICT(s) and IoT/Internet of things appearing in 2.5% and 3.4% of training materials and 4.8%, and 2.4% of programmes respectively.

Other research and innovation domains

All other research and innovation domains were each mentioned in less than 5% of all resources, indicating a lack of specificity to different types of research in programmes and training materials.

Computer Science Between Energy Savings and Waste: From Videoconferencing to Blockchain

Sustainable Security

Sustainability Transformation and Responsibility

Figure 21: The Sustainability in Computer Science public lecture series, hosted jointly by various organisations in Austria, is a source of training materials (recorded video lectures) engaging with computational and digital technologies, particularly AI

BIOENERGY WITH CARBON CAPTURE AND STORAGE (BECCS)

TECHETHOS
FUTURE • TECHNOLOGY • ETHICS

Figure 22: The TechEthos project provides training materials specific to geoengineering technologies such as Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage

Table 12: Appearance of R&I domain in the training materials

Research and innovation domain			
Absent	Present	Addressed in (X) materials	%
Behaviour change technology	Artificial intelligence	17	14,3
Digital technologies	Renewables	13	10,9
Transportation technologies	Biotechnology	9	7,6
Self-driving cars	Climate engineering	8	6,7
Gene editing	Solar radiation management	6	5,0
Negative emissions technologies	Carbon capture and storage	6	5,0
Climate smart agricultural technologies	Carbon dioxide removal	5	4,2
	Nanotechnology	5	4,2

	Internet of things	4	3,4
	Geoengineering	3	2,5
	Information and communication technologies	3	2,5
	Genetically modified organisms	3	2,5
	Nuclear	3	2,5
	Energy technologies	2	1,7
	Agricultural technologies	1	0,8

Table 13: Appearance of R&I domain in the training programmes

Research and innovation domain			
Absent	Present	Addressed in (X) programmes	%
Carbon capture and storage	Artificial intelligence	74	29,5
Solar radiation management	Biotechnology	29	11,6
Behaviour change technology	Renewables	26	10,4
Climate smart agricultural technologies	Information and communication technologies	12	4,8
Carbon dioxide removal	Energy technologies	12	4,8
Negative emissions technologies	Nanotechnology	11	4,4
	Digital technologies	9	3,6
	Nuclear	8	3,2
	Internet of things	6	2,4
	Geoengineering	4	1,6
	Gene editing	2	0,8
	Genetically modified organisms	2	0,8
	Transportation technologies	1	0,4

	Self-driving cars	1	0,4
	Climate engineering	1	0,4
	Agricultural technologies	1	0,4

Environmental and climate issues

All specific environmental or climate issues are addressed in training materials apart from soil pollution, whereas all environmental or climate issues are addressed in training programmes apart from ozone depletion and e-waste. The most frequent issue addressed in the resources is climate change (32.8% of materials and 36.7% of programmes), followed by waste (13.4% of materials and 14.7% of programmes), and pollution (12.6% of materials and 5.6% of programmes). Other issues, however, are each mentioned in less than 5% of all training materials or programmes (Table 14 and Table 15).

Environmental Ethics

Overview

Understand why ethics and morality are important in environmentalism

Discover how scientific facts and ideas are interpreted through a moral lens

Explore humanist, modernist, and other environmental perspectives

Recognise humanity's role in repairing the natural environment

Figure 23: The Environmental Ethics course, provided by the Adam Smith Center and available via the FutureLearn platform, engages with climate change alongside ethical perspectives such as ecomodernism

HOW TO MAKE YOUR LAB WORK MORE SUSTAINABLE

Workshop (in English) on March 13 and March 14, 2023

Laboratory and research work is resource-intensive and costly. Laboratory buildings use 3-5 times more energy and water than office buildings, -80°C freezers use about as much energy as a single-family home and life science laboratories worldwide generated about 5.5 million tons of plastic waste already in 2014. Such issues have increasingly come into focus in recent years.

As part of the TUD project "Green Lab Guide TU Dresden" and together with the Germany-wide project ["NACH-LABS - Reducing environmental impact and improving sustainability in laboratories at German universities"](#) at HAW Hamburg, a two-day workshop will be offered on March 13 and 14. The "NACH-LABS" project has developed a tool combining theoretical and practical content.

In this workshop, participants learn about strategies and best practice examples and work out improvement options in on-site inspections. Each team receives a checklist as a guide (based on the criteria of the LEAF assessment tool and the Ecomapping method) and documents the status quo. When the teams finished the inspections, we will discuss observations and define the next actions. In addition, the laboratories can receive LEAF certification after implementing their measures.

Figure 24: The workshop *How to make your Lab Work more Sustainable*, hosted by the Technical University of Dresden, Germany engages with the issue of research waste in the context of sustainability

Table 14: Appearance of environmental or climate issue in the training materials

Environmental or climate issue			
Absent	Present	Addressed in (X) materials	%
Soil pollution	Climate change	39	32,8
	Waste	16	13,4
	Pollution	15	12,6
	Water pollution	3	2,5
	Air pollution	3	2,5
	Biodiversity loss	2	1,7
	E-waste	2	1,7
	Ozone depletion	2	1,7
	Ocean acidification	1	0,8

Table 15: Appearance of environmental or climate issue in the training programmes

Environmental or climate issue			
Absent	Present	Addressed in (X) programmes	%
Ozone depletion	Climate change	92	36,7
E-waste	Waste	37	14,7
	Pollution	14	5,6
	Air pollution	5	2,0
	Biodiversity loss	5	2,0
	Water pollution	2	0,8
	Soil pollution	1	0,4
	Ocean acidification	1	0,4
	Ocean acidification	1	0,8

Key gaps and opportunities for training material development

1. There is a lack of engagement with theories of justice in programmes and materials related to environmental and climate considerations in research and innovation. Developing a **micromodule on justice, research and the environment** would address this gap.
2. Considering the recognized importance of virtue ethics in research integrity and ethics training, it is surprising virtue ethics is mentioned in just one resource. Developing a **micromodule on virtue and environmental and climate aspects of research and innovation** would address this gap.
3. There is little engagement with the concept of environmental risk and how to mitigate it in research and innovation practice. **Educational materials related to different types of environmental risks and methods for how to assess and mitigate these** would be appropriate.
4. There was also little engagement with concepts related to under-represented or marginalized groups or inclusion generally. **Educational materials related to whose knowledge is considered relevant, and who should be included in decision-making, in relation to environmental and climate aspects of research and innovation** would address this gap.
5. Research integrity principles were more frequently represented across the materials, which is surprising considering it is perhaps easier to make an argument that environmental and climate considerations are aspects of research ethics rather than research integrity. This indicates a need to **develop a strong argument and framing for why environmental and climate considerations should be considered as part of research ethics frameworks**.

6. The complete absence of some important principles more frequently associated with environmental and climate ethics also indicates the lack of attention to research and innovation activities within environmental and climate ethics. **A micromodule applying key environmental and climate ethics principles to research and innovation processes** would address this.

Limitations

1. The search to identify training programmes and materials was conducted in English only. Although this search did identify some non-English language resources, it is likely that relevant programmes and materials available or described in other languages were not identified by our search.
2. Variation in the use of terminology across fields was not fully accounted for in the design of our search string. For example, "socially/societally relevant research" is often used to describe ethically informed research in some fields, whilst the term "ethics" may be deliberately avoided (see here: [DRONE GAME THAT HIGHLIGHTS ETHICAL AND SUSTAINABILITY IMPLICATIONS OF DESIGN DECISIONS](#), Worldwide CDIO Initiative).
3. The content analysis process was deductive, identifying only explicitly used terms. We did not perform implicit coding, therefore some important issues not already captured by our keyword frameworks may not have been detected.
4. Although we took several steps to ensure a rigorous and consistent screening process, subjectivity in decision-making between reviewers is difficult to avoid. This is particularly relevant with regard to the "content" criterion. Sometimes the distinction between "research and innovation" and adjacent research fields such as economics/business/finance (CSR/ESG), management, policy and governance, law etc. is not completely clear. Due to this, some relevant content may have been excluded if contained within a course that did not have research or innovation as a primary focus.
5. Limited information on training programme and material content is available online, and offline training was rarely identified by our search. For example, internal departmental work by green teams, or events not amenable to analysis (i.e. biodiversity walks, hackathons, participatory learning projects, etc.) could not be fully captured using our approach.

4. Conclusion

This deliverable has provided a detailed review and gap analysis of existing RE&RI guidelines, frameworks, and training programmes and materials, focusing on their capacity to address environmental and climate concerns within R&I. The analysis of RE &RI guidelines and frameworks has highlighted significant gaps in how current guidelines and frameworks integrate environmental and climate ethics as well as their ability to address the needs of marginalised or disproportionately affected populations, including indigenous groups. This analysis revealed not only a lack of comprehensiveness in addressing climate and environmental issues but also a limited acknowledgment of these concerns within existing guidelines and frameworks. These gaps underscore the need for the development and adaptation of RE&RI resources that are aligned with the goals of the Green Transition. Key recommendations from this deliverable include embedding climate and environmental ethics more explicitly into existing frameworks, ensuring that guidelines address emerging technologies and environmental risks.

The review of existing training programmes and materials in the ERA has gathered information about programmes and courses across Europe, and freely available training materials, a curated selection of which will be available to RE4GREEN training participants. Specific gaps in training content have been identified which will act as priorities for the development of training materials in WP4. Furthermore, we have identified a large number of programmes and courses which are appropriate for the dissemination of the training materials that will be developed in WP4, magnifying the impact of the project and fostering sustainability of the project's outputs into the future.

Moving forward, these findings will inform the development of operational guidelines in Task 3.2 as well as tailored training programs in Work Package 4. This deliverable lays the groundwork for creating practical, actionable, and inclusive resources that enable stakeholders in R&I to contribute meaningfully to the European Green Deal's objectives. By bridging these gaps, RE4GREEN aims to foster a just and sustainable transition that integrates ethics and integrity at every stage of R&I.

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6. Appendices

Appendix A: List of reviewed guidelines and frameworks

Below is the complete list of the 213 guidelines and frameworks reviewed in detail, formatted as follows: *Title, Author(s)/Editor(s), Year of publication (and/or last revision), Geographical area of applicability.*

1. EU Grants. How to complete your ethics self-assessment, European Commission, 2021, European Research Area (ERA).
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4. Tollgate Principles for SRM, Stephen M. Gardiner & Augustin Fragnière, 2018, Global.
5. Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI, HLEG - AI, 2019, Europe.
6. Recommendation of the Council on Responsible Innovation in Neurotechnology, OECD, 2019, OECD countries.
7. Neuroethics Guiding Principles for the NIH BRAIN Initiative, Greely et al., 2018, Global.
8. Guidelines for Human-AI Interaction, Microsoft, 2019, Global.
9. ETHICAL GUIDANCE FOR RESEARCH WITH A POTENTIAL FOR HUMAN ENHANCEMENT, Yasemin J. Erden, PhD, University of Twente; Philip Brey, PhD, University of Twente, 2021, European Research Area (ERA).
10. PANELFIT Guidelines, PANELFIT Project, 2022, European Research Area (ERA).
11. Guide for Research Ethics Committee Members, Steering Committee on Bioethics, 2010, European Research Area (ERA).
12. Ethics By Design and Ethics of Use Approaches for Artificial Intelligence, European Commission, 2021, European Research Area (ERA).
13. International ethical guidelines for health-related research involving humans, Council for International Organizations of Medical Sciences (CIOMS), 2016, Global.
14. The Oxford Principles, S. Rayner, C. Heyward, T. Kruger, N. Pidgeon, C. Redgwell, J. Savulescu, 2013, Global.
15. The Oviedo Convention, Council of Europe, 1997, Global.
16. Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, Consortium, 2018, Netherlands.
17. UK Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, Parry et al., 2021, 2021, UK.
18. Policy on the Governance of Good Research Practice, UK Research and Innovation, 2024, UK.
19. THE CONCORDAT TO SUPPORT RESEARCH INTEGRITY, Universities UK, 2019, UK.
20. Code of Conduct for responsible Research, WHO, 2017, International.
21. Singapore Statement on Research Integrity, WCRI, 2010, International.
22. Montreal Statement on Research Integrity in Cross-Boundary Research Collaborations, WCRI, 2013, International.
23. Ethical Code of the Slovak Academy of Sciences, Slovak Academy of Sciences, 2015, Slovakia.
24. Code of Ethics for Researchers of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Czech Academy of Sciences, 2024, Czechia.
25. Danish Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, Danish Ministry of Higher Education and Science, 2014, Denmark.
26. A manifesto for reproducible science, Munafó et al., 2017, 2017, International.
27. The Finnish code of conduct for research integrity and procedures for handling alleged violations of research integrity in Finland, Finnish National Board on Research Integrity TENK, 2023, Finland.

28. Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, Royal Irish Academy, 2024, Ireland.
29. National Framework on the Transition to an Open Research Environment, Government of Ireland, 2019, Ireland.
30. Policy Statement on Research Integrity in Ireland, Irish Universities Association, 2021, Ireland.
31. National Statement on Scientific Integrity, COSCE, crue, CSIC, 2015, Spain.
32. Best Practice Guide for Research Integrity and Ethics, Austrian Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research, 2020, Austria.
33. Framework to Enhance Research Integrity in Research Collaborations, National Forum on Research Integrity, 2022, Ireland.
34. UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science, UNESCO, 2021, International.
35. Commission Recommendation (EU) 2018/790 of 25 April 2018 on access to and preservation of scientific information, European Commission, 2018, International.
36. DIRECTIVE (EU) 2019/1024 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL, European Commission, 2019, International.
37. The Research Council Policy for Open Science, The Research Council of Norway, 2020, Norway.
38. UKRI Open Access Policy, UK Research and Innovation, 2023, UK.
39. Bill and Melinda Gates Open Access Policy, Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation, 2024, International.
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51. GUIDELINES FOR RESEARCH INTEGRITY, CNR, 2019, Italy.
52. ESTONIAN CODE OF CONDUCT FOR RESEARCH INTEGRITY AGREEMENT, Estonian Research Council, 2017, Estonia.
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56. OeAWI Guidelines for Good Scientific Practice, OeAWI, 2015, Austria.
57. HEA Principles of Good Practice in Research within Irish Higher Education Institutions, Higher Education Authority, 2020, Ireland.
58. Cape Town Statement, World Conferences on Research Integrity, 2022, International.
59. General guidelines, National Research Ethics Committees, 2019, Norway.
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72. National guidelines for open science, National Library of Sweden, 2020, Sweden.
73. Ethical Code, Government of Croatia, 2015, Croatia.
74. ICH E6 (R3) Guideline on good clinical practice (GCP), European Medicines Agency, 2023, Europe.
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114. Guidance note — Research with an exclusive focus on civil applications, EC, 2021, ERA.
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158. Responsible research publication: international standards for editors, COPE, 2010, International.
159. Recommendations for the Conduct, Reporting, Editing, and Publication of Scholarly Work in Medical Journals, ICMJE, 2018, International.
160. The European Charter for Researchers The Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers, European Union, 2005, Europe.
161. Good research practice 2024, Swedish Research Council, 2024, Sweden.
162. Best Practices for Ensuring Scientific Integrity and Preventing Misconduct, OECD, 2007, International.
163. Fostering Research Integrity in Europe, European Science Foundation, 2010, Europe.
164. Ethical Guidelines for Peer Reviewers, COPE, 2013, International.
165. Guidance for Editors: Research, Audit and Service Evaluations, COPE, 2014, International.
166. Text recycling guidelines, BioMed Central, 2016, International.
167. Sharing of Information Among Editors-in-Chief Regarding Possible Misconduct, COPE, 2016, International.
168. Journals' Best Practices for Ensuring Consent for Publishing Medical Case Reports, COPE, 2016, International.
169. How to handle authorship disputes: a guide for new researchers, COPE, 2003, International.
170. Retraction Guidelines, COPE, 2019, International.
171. Cooperation between research institutions and journals on research integrity cases, COPE, 2012, International.
172. Principles of Transparency and Best Practice in Scholarly Publishing, COPE, OASPA, and WAME, 2019, International.
173. CODE OF CONDUCT FOR JOURNAL PUBLISHERS, COPE, 2024, International.
174. Stewards of Integrity Institutional Approaches to Promote and Safeguard Good Research Practice in Europe, European Science Foundation, 2008, International.
175. A Global Ethics Charter for the Protection of Healthy Volunteers in Clinical Trials, INSERM, 2024, International.
176. 7 Funder Principles for Research in Epidemics and Pandemics, GLOPID-R and UKCDR, 2020, International.
177. STM Ethical Principles for Scholarly Publishing, STM, 2014, Medical.
178. Ethics toolkit for a successful editorial office, COPE, 2022, International.
179. Citizen Science Strategy 2020 for Germany, Bürger schaffen Wissen, 2020, Germany.
180. Ten principles of citizen science, ECSA, 2022, Europe.
181. Information on the authorisation and conduct of clinical trials of medicinal products during the COVID-19 pandemic, EC, EMA, and HMA, 2022, Europe.
182. Guidance for the Submission and Conduct of Clinical Trials (CT) with Medicinal Products, Ministry of Health, 2019, Austria.
183. Nagoya Protocol, Secretary-General of the United Nations, 2010, International.
184. Standards and Operational Guidance for Ethics Review of Health-Related Research with Human Participants, WHO, 2011, International.

185. International Ethical Guidelines for Epidemiological Studies, CIOMS, 2017, International.
186. Ethical Considerations in Biomedical HIV Prevention Trials, UNAIDS/WHO, 2007, International.
187. Nuffield Council on Bioethics: the Ethics of Research related to Healthcare in Developing Countries, Nuffield Council on Bioethics, 2002, International.
188. Vaccines and Covid-19: ethical aspects on research, cost and distribution, Italian National Council for Bioethics, 2020, Italy.
189. Biomedical research for novel therapeutic treatments within the Covid-19 Pandemic: ethical issues, Italian National Council for Bioethics, 2020, Italy.
190. Research ethics during the COVID-19 pandemic: observational and, in particular, epidemiological studies, ISS COVID-19 Bioethics Working Group, 2020, Italy.
191. Special additional recommendations for Greece regarding European Instructions for management of Clinical Trials during COVID-19 pandemic, EOF, 2020, Greece.
192. Ethical Charter, National Ethics Committee of Montenegro, 2020, Montenegro.
193. CATALYZING ETHICAL RESEARCH IN EMERGENCIES Ethics guidance, lessons learned from the COVID-19 pandemic, and pending agenda, PAHO, 2020, International.
194. Guidance for ethics oversight of COVID-19 research in response to emerging evidence, PAHO, 2020, International.
195. Ensuring that COVID-19 Research is Inclusive: Guidance from the NIHR CRN INCLUDE project, NIHR, 2020, UK.
196. Guidance on minimising disruptions to the conduct and integrity of clinical trials of medicines during COVID-19, MHRA, 2020, UK.
197. Ethical standards for research during public health emergencies: Distilling existing guidance to support COVID-19 R&D, WHO, 2020, International.
198. Guidance for research ethics committees for rapid review of research during public health emergencies, WHO, 2020, International.
199. Research Ethics in International Epidemic Response, WHO, 2009, International.
200. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR CONDUCTING ETHICAL MENTAL HEALTH AND PSYCHOSOCIAL RESEARCH IN EMERGENCY SETTINGS, IASC, 2014, International.
201. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship, Wilkinson et al. (2016), 2016, International.
202. Ethics Guidelines for Environmental Epidemiologists, ISEE, 2012, International.
203. Recommended Checklist for Research Communities During the COVID-19 Pandemic for both existing and new research, UKRIO, 2020, UK.
204. Guidelines 03/2020 on the processing of data concerning health for the purpose of scientific research in the context of the COVID-19 outbreak, EDPB, 2020, Europe.
205. NRFU Ethics Principles, National Research Foundation of Ukraine, 2023, Ukraine.
206. ECSA's characteristics of citizen science, ECSA, 2020, Europe.
207. Citizen Science Strategy 2030 for Germany, Helmholtz Association, Leibniz Association, Fraunhofer Society, universities and non-academic institutions, 2022, Germany.
208. Guiding principles for public engagement, UCL, unknown, UK.
209. Ethical code for nature photography, Biodiversidad Virtual, unknown, International.
210. Recommendations for a systemic approach to ethics and integrity in research, Rok Bencin, 2024, Slovenia.
211. Scientific Research Act of North Macedonia, Government of North Macedonia, 2021, North Macedonia.
212. Guidelines for Research Ethics and Research Integrity in Citizen Science, Ozolinciute et al., 2022, Europe.
213. GUIDELINES FOR INTEGRITY IN RESEARCH AND BUSINESS COLLABORATION, Bridge Project, 2023, Europe.

Appendix B: Table of reviewed training programmes

Table 16: Table of reviewed programmes

Programme name	Level	Associated institution/project
Environmental and Climate Protection Technology	BSc	Montan Universität Leoben
Responsible Consumption and Production	Masters	Montan Universität Leoben, TU Bergakademie Freiberg, Universidad de León
Environmental Systems Sciences / Sustainability and Innovation Management (ESS / SIM)	Masters	University of Graz
Environmental Systems Sciences/Geography and Applied Human-Environment Research (USW / Geo-AMU)	Masters	University of Graz
Packaging Technology and Sustainability	Masters	FH Campus Wien
Science, Technology & Society Studies	Masters	Universität Klagenfurt
Entrepreneurship, Innovation and Sustainability	BA	Modul University
Sustainable Chemistry and Digital Processing	Masters	IMC Krems University of Applied Sciences
Engineering Responsible AI Systems	Masters	IMC Krems University of Applied Sciences
Public Lecture Series: Sustainability in Computer Science 2024		TU Wien
Bio- and Environmental Technology	Masters	FH Oberösterreich
Green Mobility	Masters	FH Campus Wien
Architecture – Green Building	Masters	FH Campus Wien
Architecture – Green Building	Bachelors	FH Campus Wien
Sustainable Packaging Technology	Bachelors	FH Campus Wien
Sustainable Management of Resources	Bachelors	FH Campus Wien

AI for Sustainable Technologies	Masters	FH Salzburg
I2P4Green course - Innovation and intellectual property for Green		IPR4SC
Business Ethics		Vorarlberg University of Applied Sciences
Climate-Responsive Building Technologies	Masters	FH Technikum Wien
Just Sustainable Cities: Perspective from Post-Socialist Eurasia 2025		ENLIGHT
Collaborating in Planetary Health		ENLIGHT
Language for Environmental Future		ENLIGHT
Science, ethics and development		Université de Namur
SCK CEN seminars on Ethics of Science and Technology		SCK CEN
EDEN Doctoral Seminar on Responsible and Sustainable Innovation Social, Technological and Operations Management, Cross-Disciplinary Perspectives'	PhD	European Institute for Advanced Studies in Management
An Introduction to Food Science		EIT Food
Risk and Disaster Management in the Anthropocene Era	Advanced master	University of Liège
Integrated Health Risk Management	Advanced master	University of Liège
AI for the Common Good	Postgraduate certificate	Vrije Universiteit Brussel
Artificial intelligence for sustainable and responsible innovation: people and culture	Postgraduate certificate	Vrije Universiteit Brussel
Third Training Event 2021		Future Arctic
ONE HEALTH: BASIC CONCEPTS		Institute of Tropical Medicine Antwerp
Understanding & Communicating Climate Science		Royal Meteorological Society
Transformative Research for Sustainability Challenges	PhD	Utrecht University, University of Twente, Wageningen University, Stockholm Resilience Centre

Climate Adaptation – Ethics		Open University of Cyprus
Energy Technologies for the Future	BSc	University of Nicosia
Environmental and Energy Management	BSc	University of Nicosia
Geographical and Environmental Field Techniques	BSc	University of Nicosia
Environmental and Energy Sciences		The Cyprus Institute
Renewable Energy Technologies		The Cyprus Institute
Public Health MPH - Environmental Health specialisation	Masters	Cyprus University of Technology
Industrial Engineering and Management		American University of Beirut
Overview of Biotechnology and Microelectronics from the Point of View of Gender, Equality and People Integration		ECOVEM
Environmental Aspects of Town and Landscape		Masaryk University
Environmental Ethics II		Masaryk University
Environmental Studies	Masters	Masaryk University
Ethical and Local Economy		Masaryk University
Framework for Sustainability		Masaryk University
Global Environmental Problems Seminar		Masaryk University
Green transition from international and european perspective		Masaryk University
Key Concepts in Environmental studies		Masaryk University
Network analysis: social, ecological, and social-ecological approaches		Masaryk University
Research Seminar V c - Philosophical and artistic-theoretical aspects of the environmental field		Masaryk University
Farm to Fork: Sustainable Food Production in a Changing Environment		EU-China-safe

Revolutionising the Food Chain with Technology		EU-China-safe
STAGE Professional Development Training		STAGE
Tropical Crop Management and Ecology	MSc	Czech University of Life Sciences Prague
FINDATA		University of Pardubice, European University, LUMSA University, Vilnius University
Ethics, Environment and Society		University of Copenhagen
Design and Innovation	MSc	Technical University of Denmark
Environmental Management, innovation and Ethics		Technical University of Denmark
Techno-Anthropology		Aalborg University
ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES TECHNOLOGY	MSc	Mesarya Technical University
IT and Green Transitions	MSc	IT University of Copenhagen
Artificial Intelligence for Sustainable Societies	MA	Tallinn University, Tampere University, Lusófona University (collaboration with Citizen OS, Estonian Anthropocene Center NGO, Lääne-Harju municipality, Inspirators!)
Planning and Analysis in Multifunctional Forestry	MSc	Estonian University of Life Sciences
Digital ethics and sustainability		Aalto University, FITech
Research Ethics for Doctoral Students	PhD	Aalto University
Sustainable Digital Life, Sustainable Societies and Digitalisation	MSc	Tampere University
Sustainability Management	MEng	Karelia University of Applied Sciences
Sustainable and Autonomous Systems (Computing Sciences)	MSc	University of Vaasa
Sociotechnical Systems and Sustainability Transitions	MSocSci	LUT University
Innovation within Planetary Boundaries		EM Lyon Business School

GREEN Graduate Program - Master of Applied Social Sciences in Energy and Environmental Transitions (ASSET): Sociology specialization		University of Pau and Pays de l'Adour
Sustainability and Social Innovation	MSc	HEC Paris
Management for Sustainability (MSc)	MSc	IESEG School of Management
Political Ecology, Degrowth and Environmental Justice (MSc)	MSc	Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona
Circular Economy and Sustainable innovation (MSc)	MSc	ESDES Business School
Research integrity, Ethics and the Sustainable Development Goals within the context of citizen science (RIECS)		ECSA
Act to think, think to act in the Anthropocene		EM Lyon Business School
Responsible Engagement		EM Lyon Business School
Data Science for Responsible Business (BSc)	BSc	EM Lyon Business School, Centrale Lyon
Responsible engineering and digital transformations	BSc	Centrale Méditerranée
Contemporary Environmental Issues		The American University of Paris
Environmental Ethics		The American University of Paris
Human-IT	BSc	ENSEA
Sustainability science	MSc	PSL Université Paris
Sustainable Development MOOC		Ulysseus University
Environmental Sciences	BSc	Leuphana University Lüneburg
Sustainability Science	Minor	Leuphana University Lüneburg
Using Drones in Environmental Sciences		CIVIS
Quantifying vulnerability to natural hazards in changing climate patterns. New perspectives and methods		CIVIS
Transdisciplinary course on sustainability sciences		CIVIS

Responsible Production and Consumption (RPC)	BSc	TU Bergakademie Freiberg
Ethics and Social Responsibility		Hochschule Pforzheim
Sustainable Management & Technology	MSc	Technical University of Munich
Berlin Ethics Certificate		Technische Universität Berlin
Responsible Innovators of Tomorrow		RWTH Aachen University, ENHANCE universities
Biofabrication	MSc	Universität Bayreuth
Geography: Society and Environment, Bachelor of Science	BSc	Universität Bayreuth
Global Food, Nutrition and Health, Master of Science	MSc	Universität Bayreuth
Advanced Materials Doctoral Program with Industry	PhD	University of Oulu
Sustainable Engineering	BSc	Leibniz Universität Hannover
Clean Energy Processes	MSc	Freidrich Alexander Universität
Responsible Innovation in Firms and Society: Digitalization, Sustainability, and More	Summer School	Katholischen Universität Eichstätt - Ingolstadt
Ethics - Economics, Law and Politics	Master	Ruhr-Universität Bochum
Environmental Ethics	MA	Universität Augsburg
Nachhaltige Innovation		Technische Universität Berlin
Natural Sciences for Sustainability	BSc	Universität Bremen
Sustainable Drug Discovery	MSc	Ghent University, Université de Lille, Medical University of Gdansk, University of Groningen
Responsibility		Hochschule Bonn-Rhein-Sieg
Digital Transformation & Sustainability	MSc	Hamburg School of Business Administration
Rethinking Environment	PhD	Ludwig Maximilians Universität München
New Mobility - Micromobility	MSc	PFH Private University of Applied Sciences

Science, Technology, Society — Science and Technology Studies	MSc	National and Kapodistrian University of Athens
Science, Technology, Society — Science and Technology Studies, Environment/Sustainability lecture series and workshops	MSc	National and Kapodistrian University of Athens
Environmental Science	BSc	Perrotis College
Biolaw and Biotechnology: The crossroads of Science and Regulation		European Law and Governance School
Advanced techniques in vertical farming: From LED lighting to plant nutritio		Relief
Innovation and Entrepreneurship Short Lecture Series 2024		EURECA PRO European University
Modern Technologies for the Near-Zero Waste Processing of Low-Grade Primary Ores and Secondary Raw Materials		EURECA PRO European University
SMACITE Training Programme		SMACITE
GreenCool Online Course		GreenCool
Innovation and Intellectual Property for Green		IPR4SC
Human Ecology	MA	University of Pécs
Sustainability		OTTER
Responsible Business and Sustainability	MSc	Trinity College Dublin
Creativity Innovation&Teamwork	BSc	Munster Technological University
Environmental Science and Sustainable Technology	BSc	Munster Technological University
Green Team Project	BSc	Munster Technological University
Environmental Ethics & Global Moral Issues		Dublin City University
Green Data Science		UCD Dublin
LEES - Law, Ethics and Economics for Sustainability	PhD	Università Degli Studi di Milano

SIS2E - Strategic Innovation for Sustainable and Smart Ecosystems	PhD	Università Degli Studi di Milano Bicocca
Ethics of research, responsible research and innovation and science communication	PhD	Università Degli Studi di Pavia
Law, Digital Innovation and Sustainability	MSc	LUISS Graduate School
GIScience per la Giustizia Climatica		Climate Justice Jean Monnet Centre of Excellence
Ethics in Chemistry		Sapienza Università di Roma
Current issues in communication and media research – Communicating for the environment in the age of ecological crisis		CHARM-EU, Eötvös Loránd Tudományegyetem
Bio-inspiration Essentials		CHARM-EU, Universiteit Utrecht
Environmental Chemistry: Impact of food production on environmental compartments		CHARM-EU, Julius-Maximilians-Universität Würzburg
Global Challenges for Sustainability	MSc	CHARM-EU
Eco-Innovation, Social Responsibility, and Sustainable Management		Stockholm School of Economics in Riga
Environmental Innovation Technologies	BEng	Liepaja University
Environmental Science	MSc	University of Latvia
Biotechnology and environmental friendly technologies		University of Latvia
Sustainable Business and Green Technologies	BSc	SMK College of Applied Sciences
Politics of Global Challenges	BSc	Vilnius University
Environmental Ethics	MA	University of Malta
Ethics and the Environment		University of Amsterdam
Philosophy of Science, Technology & Society	MSc	University of Twente
Global Sustainability Science	BSc	Utrecht University
Sustainability Transitions (Innovation Management)	MSc	Eindhoven University of Technology
Ethics and Animal Sciences	PhD	Wageningen University

Ethics for Designers: Concepts and Tools	PhD	Wageningen University
Ethics in Plant and Environmental Sciences	PhD	Wageningen University
Philosophy and Ethics of Food Science and Technology	PhD	Wageningen University
4TU.Responsible Sustainability Challenge	Masters	4TU.Federation, Delft University of Technology, Eindhoven University of Technology, University of Twente, Wageningen University
Healthy Environments and Sustainability in the EU		Maastricht University
Ethics of Innovation	Bachelors	Leiden University, Delft University of Technology, Erasmus University Rotterdam
Ethics, Culture and Biotechnology	Bachelors	Leiden University, Delft University of Technology, Erasmus University Rotterdam
Introduction to Responsible Innovation	Bachelors	Leiden University, Delft University of Technology, Erasmus University Rotterdam
Responsible Innovation	Minor	Leiden University, Delft University of Technology, Erasmus University Rotterdam
Ethics and Impacts of Global Interventions		Delft University of Technology
Learning Lines	BSc	Delft University of Technology
Ethics of Technological Risk		Delft University of Technology
Solving Sustainability Challenges with Te Ao Māori (Māori World View)		Wintec, Te Pukenga - New Zealand Institute of Skills and Technology
Water Ethics		Delft University of Technology
Climate Ethics	MSc	Delft University of Technology
Environmental Ethics	MSc	Delft University of Technology
Ethics of Transportation	MSc	Delft University of Technology
The engineer in society		Delft University of Technology
Sustainability ethics and sustainable behaviour	MSc	Rotterdam School of Management Erasmus University

Sustainability transitions and responsible innovation	Master	Eindhoven University of Technology
Co-Creating Sustainable Cities		Delft University of Technology
Inclusive Energy Systems: Exploring Sustainable Energy for All		Delft University of Technology
Rethink the City: New approaches to Global and Local Urban Challenges		Delft University of Technology
Sustainable Business Transition	Masters	Hogeschool Utrecht
Frugal Innovation for Sustainable Goal Development	Minor	Leiden University
Sustainable Innovation		ESG-UP
Trainings on digital innovation of heritage	PhD	The University of Veterinary Medicine and Pharmacy in Košice
FVO: Environmental Protection and Eco-technologies	Masters	Faculty of Environmental Protection, Velenje
ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION		B&B College of Sustainable Development (Company - not a University)
Environmental Management	Bachelors	University of Nova Gorica
Introduction to Responsible & Sustainable Innovatin		Universitat Rovira i Virgili, Tarragon, Responsible Research and Innovation Learning
Ethics in Responsible and Sustainable Innovation	Undergraduate and graduate	Universitat Rovira i Virgili, Tarragon, Responsible Research and Innovation Learning
Postgraduate in Environmental Ethics	Post grad	Ramón Llull University
Sustainability Science and Technology	Masters	Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya
Modeling Climate Futures: Science, Economics, Ethics and Policy	MSc	Chalmers University of Technology
Crisis, sustainability and innovation	Post grad	Swedish Defence University
Sustainable Technology	MSc	KTH Royal Institute of Technology
Sustainable development: values, technology in society, and the researcher	MSc	Chalmers University of Technology

Lecture series on climate protection – University of Innsbruck		University of Innsbruck
Universitätsweites Basismodul: Verantwortung in Wissenschaft und Beruf	Bachelors	University of Graz
Global Minds	Bachelors	Ghent University
Socio-technical dimensions of Renewable Energy	Masters	Technical University of Denmark
Nordic master in sustainable ICT solutions	Masters	Aalborg University
Technology Governance and Sustainability	MA	Tallinn University of Technology
Spatial Justice	MSc	Maynooth University
Food Entrepreneurship, Sustainability and Innovation Practices: a Comparison between Africa and the Nordic Countries		University of Helsinki, Ruralia Institute.
Sustainability sciences	Bachelors	Paris Sciences et Lettres – PSL Research University Paris
Governance of Technology and Innovation	MA	RWTH Aachen University
Sustainable Energy and Process Engineering	MSc	Technical University of Berlin
Environmental Sciences and Engineering	Masters	Brno University of Technology
Environmental Management and Sustainability Science	Masters	Aalborg University
CIRCPRO	PhD	Tallinn University of Technology
Environmental Change and Global Sustainability	Masters	University of Helsinki
Sustainable Environments	MSc	University of Galway
Carbon Literacy		University College Cork
Sustainability module		University College Cork
Climate Justice Living Lab - Palermo		University of Palermo, Climate Justice Living Lab
designing for transition: ecodesign, circularity and regenerative solutions - ed.I	Masters	Politecnico di Milano

Sustainable and Circular Systems	PhD	Polytechnic University of Turin
Ecodesign	Masters	Marche Polytechnic University
T4EU Bootcamp in Bulgaria		Vytautas Magnus University
Gender and Diversity for Sustainable Worlds	BSc	Wageningen University
MOOC Transformative Citizen Science for Sustainability		Wageningen University
Ecosystem Thinking		The University of A Coruña
Technology, Power and the Future of Humanity	Bachelors	Uppsala University
Applied Environmental Science - Ecosystem Services and Nature Resource Management	BSc	Halmstad University
The Process of Research: Qualitative Methods, Data Analysis and Academic Writing	Masters	Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences
Why are nonhuman animals victims of harm?		The Open University
Water Engineering Ethic		Harbin Institute of Technology
Edible Insects		National Taiwan University
Environmental Management & Ethics		Technical University of Denmark
Exploring philosophy: faking nature		The Open University
Environmental Ethics		Adam Smith Center
Ecology and Environmental Ethics – Problems and Perspectives		Consortium for Educational Communication
Community Science - Science for Climate and Justice		American Geophysical Union
Research and Innovation for Climate Neutral and Sustainable Cities		Lund University
Technology Metals for a Green Future		University of Exeter
MOOC Responsible Innovation: Ethics, Safety and Technology		?
Introduction to Digitization & (Geo)Data	BSc	TU Delft

Climate Solutions: UAE		University of Edinburgh
From Climate Science to Action		The World Bank
Bioeconomy: How Renewable Resources Can Help the Future of Our Planet (FutureLearn)		University of York, BioYorkshire
Climate Change Mitigation in Developing Countries		University of Cape Town
Ethical Dimensions of Renewable Energy and Sustainability Systems	BSc	Pennsylvania State University
Environment and Society in a Changing World	BSc	Pennsylvania State University
Controversies in the Earth Sciences	BSc	Pennsylvania State University
Enhancing International Scientific Cooperation: Arctic Science and Technology Advice with Ministries		UNITAR
Open and Transparent Forest Data: Innovation and Technology for Climate Action		Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
Environmental Philosophy		National Programme on Technology Enhanced Learning
Environmental Awareness and Conservation		EduRise
Risks to the environment, animals, plants, and ecosystems		ROSiE
Environmental Values and Sustainable Transformations	Minor	University of Twente
Environmental & Energy Management	Masters	University of Twente
Sustainability & Justice	Masters	University of Twente
Technē, Ecology, Ethics - Student training programme		European University of Technology
Climate change	BA	Radboud University
The Bigger Picture (in environmental and climate sciences): Connecting your research to the wider context	MSc	SENSE
Understanding justice and fairness in energy transitions		Utrecht University

Appendix C: Table of reviewed training materials

Table 17: Table of reviewed training materials

Material name	Material type (case study?)	Associated institution/project
Climate Change and Climate Crisis. Transformative Concepts and Innovations		Universität Wien
Climate Change and Climate Crisis. Future concepts and innovations		Universität Wien
Climate Change and Climate Crisis. Interdisciplinary Perspectives		Universität Wien
GINEVRA MasterClass 1 - Responsible Innovation		GINEVRA
Citizen science in environmental monitoring: a framework for ethical issues		Österreich forscht
Creating Circularity for Critical Raw Materials		Boku University
Living Well within Limits		Boku University
Reflections on the research project 'Ethics and Energy': how the turn to bottom-up climate governance also rendered non-state actors responsible for climate change		Boku University
Transforming Tomorrow: Moving From Climate Emergency to Prosperity		Boku University
Extractivism, Extreme oil and Pipelines : socio-ecological conflicts in North America		Boku University
Alternatives to the jobs vs environment dilemma. Degrowth and the Liberation of Work		Boku University
Resource efficiency - Delivering more service with less energy, material and impact		Boku University
Research morning FBE - 'Ethics and Sustainability'		University of Antwerp
Circular Economy & Environment		ENLIGHT

Circular Economy: The Future of Sustainable Living		Young Universities for the Future of Europe
The environmental sustainability of space sciences		CNRS Terre&Univers institut de recherche en astrophysique et planétologie (IRAP - OMP)
ENRICHMENT COURSE ENVIRONMENTAL ETHICS		ECO-Center
Academic Course 1		ECO-Center
Academic Course 2		ECO-Center
ISDRS Conference - One Health, SDGs and ethical conflicts track		International Sustainable Development Research Society
Geoengineering: Climate Control		EduFACE
Responsible research and innovation and participation in research projects		Milieu
Environmental Philosophy Summer School		CETE-P
AI versus Climate? Debate on Ecological AI in Central Europe		CETE-P
AI and Extinction through a Welfarist Lens		CETE-P
MYSLI A ŽIJ!: human-technology-world relations and the global ecosystem		CETE-P
How (Un)Fair Are New Technologies?		CETE-P
Urban Aesthetics		CETE-P
Echology': Field Philosophy and Indigenous Australia		CETE-P
Can Technology Save the Planet?		CETE-P
Self-Nudging Tools		Nudging for SDGs
Developing Science Infographics for the General Public		STAGE
Science Communication Toolkit		STAGE
New Genomic Techniques in Plants		Novo Nordisk Foundation Science Cluster
Module 3: Responsibility		High-Flier

Teaching cases	Case study	COMPASS
Entrepreneurship for Sustainable Precision Agriculture - Policy and Management module		SPARKLE
Where does a fork come from?		AGEMERA
Ecosystem Mapping		Mission Lab, University of Limerick
Empathy Map		Mission Lab, University of Limerick
Value Proposition		Mission Lab, University of Limerick
Futures Triangle		Mission Lab, University of Limerick
Systems Iceberg		Mission Lab, University of Limerick
Innovation Portfolio		Mission Lab, University of Limerick
Iterative Inquiry		Mission Lab, University of Limerick
Impact Map		Mission Lab, University of Limerick
Three Horizons		Mission Lab, University of Limerick
Theory of Change		Mission Lab, University of Limerick
Scenario Development		Mission Lab, University of Limerick
Collaboration Model		Mission Lab, University of Limerick
Responsible Technology Playbook		United Nations, Thoughtworks
Lecture 4 - Environmental Ethics 1		Morality Matters, John Forge
Lecture 5 - Environmental Ethics 2		Morality Matters, John Forge
Lecture 6 - Environmental Ethics 3		Morality Matters, John Forge
Gender-responsive evaluation for a sustainable future for all - Tool 8: Identifying the gender implications of environmental impacts		European Institute for Gender Equality
Gender-responsive evaluation for a sustainable future for all - Tool 9: Embedding gender equality throughout your fieldwork		European Institute for Gender Equality
Techno-Moral Vignettes	Case study	PRISMA, Rathenau Institute

Licara NanoScan		PRISMA, TNO
Gender Equality Toolkit		PRISMA, Australian Government
Sustainability Method Selection Tool		PRISMA, Dutch Government
Data quality in citizen science	Case study	ROSiE
Teaching		Monika Seyfried
Designing Ethical Futures		Monika Seyfried
Designing Ethical Futures		Monika Seyfried
Sustainable Management: Tools for Tomorrow		Too4To
Lesson 7 - ECO innovation - driven		Projectdriven
ECO-I Manual		UNEP
Ethics of Genome Editing		UNESCO
Workshop on Techno-Ethical Case Research & Writing - KInIT		Ethics4Challenges
The role of ethics in research		University of Primorska, ResBios
Reserch Methodology of the Project		Rights for Ecosystem Services Project
DRONE GAME THAT HIGHLIGHTS ETHICAL AND IMPLICATIONS OF DESIGN DECISIONS		Ecole Polytechnique Federale de Lausanne
The battle for truth in water, climate, and environment		Stockholm International Water Institute
Creative Sustainability-in-Practice		Cyprus University of Technology
How to make your lab work more sustainable		TU Dresden
Telling the Future: Re-Imagining the Technosphere		University of Konstanz
Concepts of intervention science applied to global challenges Summer School		Eötvös Loránd University
Trieste Next festival delle ricerca scientifica		Trieste City of Knowledge, University of Trieste

Roundtable on open access and climate justice		Erasmus University
Climate colloquium		University of Twente
Workshop mining matters		University of Twente
Green transition: Advancing academia's role in sustainable innovation		Athena European University
How does an extractivist frontier come to being?		Autonomous University of Barcelona
New perspectives in plant ethics		University of Murcia
Rights of nature and naturalist ontology: do we need indigenous people to defend the rights of nature?		University of Murcia
Declaration of Ethical Principles in relation to Climate Change		UNESCO
Y/our Ethics Decide		TechEthos
Should scientists share the data in climate science?	Case study	ROSiE
Y/our Ethics Decide: Climate Engineering		TechEthos
Y/our Ethics Decide: Stratospheric Aerosol		TechEthos
Y/our Ethics Decide: Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage		TechEthos
Y/our Ethics Decide: Afforestation and Reforestation		TechEthos
Y/our Ethics Decide: Ocean Fertilisation		TechEthos
Y/our Ethics Decide: Ground-based Albedo Modification		TechEthos
Y/our Ethics Decide: Direct Air Carbon Capture and Storage		TechEthos
Responsible Research and Innovation made simple: A comprehensive toolbox for embedding RRI in SHARED GREEN DEAL activities		Fraunhofer ISI, WECF, Anglia Ruskin University
Guiding Principles for planning and implementing responsible social experiments		Fraunhofer ISI, WECF, Anglia Ruskin University
Guidelines for considering gender		Fraunhofer ISI, WECF, Anglia Ruskin University

Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) tools		Fraunhofer ISI, WECF, Anglia Ruskin University
Coloring Connections. Researching Gender, Intersectionality, and Health in the Climate Crisis		Petra Verdonk, Katinka Feijs
T-learning research tool: Contextual profiling		Rhodes University, National Research Foundation, Transformations to Sustainability, International Social Sciences Council
Les crises environnementales : rôle et positionnement de la recherche		Labos 1.5
Connaissances essentielles sur les crises environnementales (sciences de l'environnement et sciences humaines et sociales)		Labos 1.5
Les outils de la communauté scientifique pour prendre en compte son empreinte carbone		Labos 1.5
Quelle recherche pour les transitions écologiques ?		Labos 1.5
Compostor	Case study	European University of Technology
Drinks automatic distributor	Case study	European University of Technology
Juror 13: Ethics and the Technology on the Farm	Case study	European University of Technology
Microwave oven	Case study	European University of Technology
Plastic bottles recovery machine	Case study	European University of Technology
Smartphone	Case study	European University of Technology
Solar panels	Case study	European University of Technology
Tetrapack cartons	Case study	European University of Technology
Washing machine	Case study	European University of Technology
Waste incinerator	Case study	European University of Technology
Case Study Guttannen: Perspective 3 - ethics: Ethical case analysis - a principlist methodology	Case study	Knowledge for Climate
Transforming Indigenous/Non-Indigenous Research Partnerships		UKRI

FOOTPRINT IN THE SAND: A DISCUSSION ON INDIGENOUS AND NON-INDIGENOUS RESEARCH COLLABORATION		UKRI
De/Colonisation		UKRI
sustainable digital infrastructures		IT University of Copenhagen

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D6.5 Checklists, factsheets and gender glossary

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6.	Partner	Aarhus University	AU	Denmark
7.	Partner	National Technical University of Athens	NTUA	Greece
8.	Partner	European Association of Research Managers & Administrators	EARMA	European network
9.	Partner	European Citizen Science Association	ECSA	European network
10.	Partner	Korean University	KU	Korea
11.	Partner	Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona	UAB	Spain
12.	Partner	University of Cape Town	UCT	South Africa
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INTRODUCTION

Research Ethics and Integrity for the GREEN transition (RE4GREEN) is a three-year project funded by the European Union's Horizon Grants for research. The project aims to develop a framework that will address **ethics and integrity concerns** within the green transition. **Women Engage for a Common Future** is an **ecofeminist** network organisation and a partner on the RE4GREEN project, whose role is predominantly to **strengthen the capacity of the partners** to implement ecofeminist analysis and action throughout the project's implementation.

The United Nations 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development sets out 17 sustainable development goals (SDGs), which focus on key goals for sustainability the Member States should work towards. The SDGs are interconnected, as is shown in the factsheet here, issues of **health** (SDG 3), **gender** (SDG 5) and **climate change** (SDG 13) are **impossible** to address in **siloed** approaches. At the same time, the European Union historically has not made such connections, for example the **European Green Deal** does little to incorporate the socially transformative analysis that was outlined in *inter alia* the **EU's Gender Equality Strategy** and the **Anti Racism Action Plan**.

With this context in mind then, and also considering **RE4GREEN's aims** as well as **positionality** as an EU funded project, the subsequent documents aim to **stimulate discussion** among the consortium for how we can address structural inequalities within the green transition. **The glossary** outlines key definitions that will be worked with throughout the capacity strengthening, and the **fact sheet** gives entry points for thinking about the connection between social identities, the green transition, and research ethics. The **two factsheets** provide areas for reflection on report writing, in order to understand how the research we do can reproduce inequalities. **These documents will provide a basis for future consortium training** for the partners to engage with ecofeminist issues as they arise both in the project implementation and in thinking about the green transition more broadly.

GLOSSARY

No definition is neutral, and the definitions given below are based on the positionality of the authors. This is a living document and will be edited as the RE4GREEN project develops.

Coloniality refers to discourses and practices that reproduce **racial-colonial power relations** and structures. **Quijano (2000)** coined the term to provide an analytical frame for understanding how racial classifications shape modernity. This means the classification of colonised people's ways of being and thinking are considered **naturally inferior** to White European colonisers'. An example of this is how **Western liberal democratic values** continue to be imposed and used as a gauge that all countries are measured up against.

Coloniality and Gender **Lugones (2010)** gives an illuminating history of gender as a colonial construct, as colonised people were constructed as 'having' a sex, but not having a gender. She argues that gender was inexplicably bound up with ideas of temporality; the **"civilised coloniser"** versus the **"backwards colonial subject."** By constructing the colonised subject as sexed, they could be sexualised, which led to both the creation of the "over sexual colonised female" and the "feminine colonised male" who could be controlled through, inter alia, sexual violence. **Gender was something that was achieved** for those who became civilised under the colonial ideal of the European man (and to a lesser extent the European woman), through which colonised peoples were subverted.

Hetero Patriarchy is the social system we live in, in which **men hold power**, predominating in roles of political leadership, moral authority, social privilege, and control of property. Patriarchy is based on a **dichotomous binary distinction** between men and women, where the differences between both categories become naturalised. For example, **men are portrayed as being "rational" and women are contrasted as "emotional"**, this means that men's expression of emotions are understood to be more logical and these characteristics are considered more valuable. At the same time, **heterosexism pairs together men and women**, meaning any experiences of gender or sexuality out of this binary distinction are suppressed and made unnatural. This is why many scholars and activists have used the word **"queer"** to explain their ways of challenging this binary system of heteropatriarchy.

Neo/liberal Feminism Liberal feminism **centres** the **experience of whiteness** and the experiences of women in the colonial core. It argues for "giving a voice to the voiceless" where white women in Europe **dictate an understanding of what the goals of feminism should be**. Neoliberal Feminism is hyper individualised and focuses on **individual women's "empowerment"** and ability to succeed in a neoliberal world.

Ecofeminism is a movement that combines **ecological sustainability** and feminist principles, arguing that the exploitation of nature and the oppression of women are interconnected. It emphasises that **environmental degradation** and **social inequality** are both rooted in **patriarchal** and **capitalist** systems, and calls for the **dismantling of these structures** to promote justice for both the environment and marginalised communities. Ecofeminists advocate for a holistic approach that integrates environmental care with the pursuit of gender equality and social justice.

Environmental Justice is an approach to environmental politics that addresses the impacts of **colonialism** and **capitalism** on the environment. This includes ensuring that **wealthy colonial countries bear (financial) responsibility** for the climate crisis as well as acknowledging that those who live in the **global periphery often bear the brunt** of the impacts of climate change.

Intersectionality as a term was first coined by Black legal scholar **Kimberle Crenshaw in 1989**. Crenshaw highlighted how African American women could make claims of **discrimination under sexism or racism but not both**. Crenshaw then expanded this work to highlight the **intersection** of the identities of "Black" and "Woman" in the specific context of the U.S. Since then, intersectionality has become uplifted into many contexts within feminist writing. This is **something to be wary of** in some cases, for example additive intersectionality is a **"diversity within"** model, whereby a predefined social group (e.g., women) is sought to be expanded on through **"diversity" principles**. This model assumes that merely adding more diverse groups into a space will automatically address the structural issues of racism within that space. Such work does not tackle the hegemonic status quo of white liberal feminism. **(Christoffersen and Emejulu, 2023)**

De-colonialism examines the ways in which **western modernity has made natural western domination**. It is linked to Latin American scholars **Lugones** and **Quijano**, as well as world systems theory. Through "delinking" (see **Mignolo 2007**), de-colonialism offers new ways to reimagine a world that is a radical alternative to the colonial one we exist in today.

Post-colonialism seeks to analyse colonial discourse and culture using a lens that unpacks and fundamentally challenges the way the colonial subject is presented in western discourses. It was developed by scholars such as **Edward Said, Homi Bhabha, and Gayatri Spivak**.

Standpoint Theory is a **feminist application of Marxist theory** that indicates the 'consciousness' as an oppressed group in understanding both the position of the oppressed, the advantages of an oppressor and the process of recognising that others suffer the same forms of oppression as you.

Gender Transformative Approaches are strategies and interventions aimed at **transforming gender relations** to promote equity and to challenge structural heteropatriarchy. Often facilitated through collecting **gender-dissaggregated data**, to address the data gap and understand gendered realities. Gender transformative policies **go further than gender sensitive policies** (which reflect awareness of gender inequalities), and **gender responsive policies** (which aim to address gender inequalities).

Gender Mainstreaming is the practice of assessing and addressing the **gendered implications** of any planned action, including **legislation, policies, or programs**, to ensure that gender equality is considered and promoted.

Feminist Facilitation Techniques Methods used in group discussions and trainings that prioritise **accessible, inclusive, and equitable** engagement, often highlighting the voices and **experiences of marginalised groups**. [See our feminist moderation course.](#)

FURTHER READING

Below are some further readings as well as texts referenced in this Glossary. Those that have a clickable link are journal articles, and those without are books.

Ecofeminism

- Ourkiya, Asmae (2020) "[Queering Ecofeminism: Towards an Anti-Far-Right Environmentalism](#)"
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De-colonialism

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Intersectionality

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Factsheet: Linking Gender, Climate Change and Research

What is Ecofeminism?

Ecofeminism argues that the **structures that created the climate crisis** also create **gendered social injustice**. For example, colonialism and **patriarchy** create a hierarchy that prioritises the **non-disabled white European man** and **subverts** people of other categories such as **women in all their diversity, queer people, disabled people and people of colour**. At the same time, white European men were the principal actors in the **rapid industrialisation of Europe** through the violent **exploitation of colonies**, and the subsequent environmental destruction and climate crisis. Through violently extracting **natural resources** as well as the **labour of people** from the colonies, Europe continues to foster its own expansion and development whilst ensuring colonised countries **do not** have access to the **resources to tackle climate change**. This means that structurally excluded communities who are most impacted by climate change are at the **forefront** of the **ecofeminist** fight for a gender and climate just future.

Differentiated Impact of Climate Change and Environmental Degradation in Europe

The differentiated impacts of climate change are not just confined to disparities between the Global North and South but also manifest within Europe by disproportionately impacting those groups who continue to be excluded from Europe's development.

→ **LGBTQ+ people and community enclaves** are disproportionately located in high-risk areas prone to **flooding, poor air quality, mosquito-borne diseases, and extreme heat**, all of which are scenarios that are increasing due to climate change. ([source](#))

→ The EU's agricultural free trade agreements lead to **mechanised cash cropping**, which **crowds women out of the farms** in which they hold knowledge. At the same time, these policies negatively impact the climate through **deforestation, reduction of biodiversity and greenhouse gas emissions**. ([source](#) - p. 71)

→ Skin lightening creams are marketed to (primarily) women of colour to achieve the **European beauty standard of whiteness**. Such creams are ill regulated on the EU market and have been found to contain high traces of **mercury** which can cause **psychological and skin disorders** as well as being **damaging** to the **environment**. ([source](#) - p. 138)

→ Women often make **several shorter trips** on public transport (known as **trip chaining**), while men are more likely to travel from **point A to B**. This is because women's trip patterns are more likely to revolve around care e.g., taking children to school, looking after older relatives, or household grocery shopping. Whereas men are more likely to go to work and then return. Yet the design of the **EU's green transport policies** continues to be based on **masculine mobility patterns**. ([source](#) - p16)

→ **Older women** are more disproportionately affected by **energy poverty** – as due to the **pension gap** and the **gender pay gap**, they are more likely to be unable to **afford to heat** their homes, as well as being **more sensitive to heat and cold** stresses due to their physiology, and more at **risk of death** from heat related conditions (if they were assigned female at birth). ([source](#))

Ecofeminism and Research Ethics

Traditional research methodology assumes a “**researcher**” and an “**object**” of study. In much of the research around the effects of climate change, **nature and the environment** are treated as an object of study. Similarly, **communities who are most affected by climate change** are also treated as objects of study within academia. The colonial structure of academia means that the most prestigious research institutes with the most funding are based in the Global North. Additionally, due to **patriarchal structures**, and despite numerous initiatives to improve the representation of women, the senior positions are still dominated by white men. When researching the Global South, often the “**data**” of objects of study are **taken from their context by researchers based in the Global North** for their own academic profit, with **little to no benefit** accruing to research participants in the Global South.

Structural Inequality and Research Ethics

Whilst there have been efforts to develop new research paradigms to tackle the colonial and patriarchal structures in academia, many of the structural issues remain. These can be illustrated in persisting structural barriers, research gaps and inequalities in what is considered “valid” research.

➔ A study on journals published in the Web of Science directory found that over half of journals **come from just 5 countries** (UK, US, New Zealand, Australia, Canada), with **96.17% publishing in English only**. ([source](#))

➔ A study on patterns of authorship over the period 2005–2015 in ‘leading’ economics journals that publish regularly on Africa found that while the journals have **30% of their content about Africa**, **only 3% of their editorial boards are based on the continent**. ([source](#))

➔ In Europe, although **women** represent nearly **half of grade C positions** (researcher, assistant professor), **grade A positions** that include full professors and directors of research comprised only **26.2% women in 2018**. ([source](#))

➔ While **work-related cancers** cause many deaths every year due to chemical exposure, those that occur in **male dominated fields** (e.g., mining) remain a research focus, whereas **women dominated** sectors (e.g., nail salons in Europe/the USA that are made up of primarily women migrant workers from East Asia) remain under-researched. When research is conducted, it is rarely on chronic/long term exposure and takes **75 kilo white men aged 25-36 as the basis of study**. (source - Invisible Women, Chapter 5)

Those Most Affected at the Forefront of Change!

Whilst we cannot immediately eradicate colonial and patriarchal dynamics in our work, we can highlight initiatives where those most affected are at the forefront of change, and rethink traditional extractive approaches of “researcher” versus “the researched”.

The **Indigenous Saami people** of Sweden have been at the forefront in organising **strikes against geoengineering** projects that were done without consultation of their communities. ([source](#) - p. 24)

In France, near the city of Lille, the Hellemmes-Ronchin reception area was established to serve as **temporary accommodation** for gens du voyage (traveller communities) passing through the region. However, since its inception, families have **settled there permanently** due to the **lack of viable alternatives**, a trend seen in many reception areas across France. The **women’s collective** of Hellemmes-Ronchin was formed in order to **achieve recognition of the health issues tied to pollution in the area**, as well as raising awareness of the **environmental racism** traveller communities in France face. ([source](#), p. 27)

Just Stop Oil protesters disrupted **pride** in London, England in 2023 due to polluters sponsoring the event. The protestors stated that these corporations were using pride to promote a good public image, which is in direct tension with the fact that **queer communities in the Global South** often bear the brunt of climate change. ([source](#))

Environment and Development Action (ENDA) Colombia works with **women recyclers / waste pickers** to understand the **unique challenges** they face (e.g., violence in working on the street). These collectives **challenge existing capitalist models** and promote solidarity economy models. ([source](#) - p.35)

Honor the Earth is an **indigenous ecofeminist organisation** in the USA that campaigns against sexual violence in extraction zones. In the **Brakken oil fields, North Dakota** and the **Tar Sands of Alberta**, extractivist **violence against nature** runs parallel to **violence against Indigenous** women. The collective requested a **formal intervention** by the **United Nations** and their submission document provides **research on the relationship between oil booms and sex trafficking**. ([source](#) - p. 87)

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Checklist One: How to draft a Gender Transformative Report

Checklist Summary

Positionality

- Where am I speaking from?
- What people/organisations have been present in the work here?
- Are we all on the same page?

Accessibility

- Who is the audience of this document?
- Have I taken steps to ensure this document is readable by everybody?

Applicability

- What contexts am I extrapolating to?
- Who am I assuming is the default person in the report writing?

What is a Gender Transformative Report?

Reports reflect the **positionalities** and the **politics** of the **people** and **organisations** who produce them. It is important when drafting a report that you have considered how to express your work in a way that **takes into consideration these positionalities**. It is **okay** if you have **not managed to address all power relations/structures** of inequality in your work! Transformative report writing is about **acknowledging** this and **expressing** your work in a way that **makes sense of what you have done** for both yourself and the reader.

Questions to ask yourself before writing

Positionality

Where am I speaking from?

You can start by asking yourself about your own position in relation to the topic at hand. What is your **personal interest** in the topic? How is this informed by your **experiences**? What are the **main theoretical approaches/understandings** you are drawing on? What **people/organisations have been present** in the work here?

Your work is not just based on your own personal politics but also the **politics of your organisation** and those who fund you. For example, if you are **based in the EU** and you are writing a research report on the **Western Balkans**, this would represent different dynamics than if you were writing about research conducted in **North Africa**. Whilst your work will often have a **disclaimer** saying it does not represent the views of the funder, it is still vital to **reflect on the purpose of your work**. For example, if you were doing EU funded research in the Western Balkans, are the outcomes affected by the **EU accession process**? In North Africa, would **colonial dynamics between researcher and subject** - that need to be reflected upon - be present?

Are we all on the same page?

If you are writing with **multiple authors**, it is good to **reflect on the questions in this checklist beforehand** and discuss **common definitions** of terms that will be used. By having a common understanding of definitions that reflect your positionality, you will not only produce work that is **clear** but also create a space for **productive dialogue** during the writing process.

Accessibility

Who is the audience of this document?

Thinking about the audience of the document is commonplace in research writing, but in order to apply feminist practices to this, you should reflect on **what you are assuming about your audience**. For example, are they **fluent in English**? Are they **familiar with** the words or **jargon** you use in your work? It is important to **always spell out jargon**, and if you have the funding – **pay somebody to translate your work** into multiple languages, depending on your audience's demands.

As **feminist theorist bell hooks** argues in their work "**Feminist theory from margin to center**", transformative writing should be **easily understood by a wide range of people** regardless of background:

A feminist essay with revolutionary ideas written in a complicated, abstract manner using the jargon of a specific discipline, will not have the impact it should have on the consciousness of women and men because it will probably be read by only a small group of people. (hooks, 1984 p. 111)

Have I taken steps to ensure this document is readable by everybody?

Accessibility is not just about jargon and ensuring you speak in plain English, but also considering the fact that **not everyone accesses documents in the same way**. For example, people who use **screen readers** benefit from having **image descriptions** of the pictures in your report so the screen reader can describe them. Similarly, **certain fonts and colours are more accessible than others**. Choose font colours that **contrast** with the **background** so they are readable, and fonts that are **not in cursive** (e.g., **sans serif** or **arial** are accessible fonts).

Applicability

What contexts am I extrapolating to?

There is a tendency in **European thinking** to imagine that our research can "**teach**" people from **outside Europe**. This **must be unlearnt** if we are to engage properly with the role of the EU in **colonial epistemic production**. E.g., if you are writing a report on EU environmental policy with NGOs based in Europe, you **should not claim to have applicability** to contexts you do not know – **unless you can prove** these tangible links.

Moreover, it is important to think about **why** you would imagine that lessons learnt in a specific context in Europe would be beneficial elsewhere? Viewing the EU as a place in which **universal lessons can be learnt**, whereas **abroad is considered "local"** or specific case studies, **reproduces colonial dynamics**.

Who am I assuming is the default person in the report writing?

Often feminist critique will highlight how there is a "**default man**" that pervades our thinking e.g., the assumption that being a **white, non-disabled, middle class European man** is the norm. This can also be reflected in **Eurocentric thinking**, for example talking about "**citizens**" of certain places **excludes stateless people or refugees**, or when projects that focus on democracy say that people are "**losing faith in the EU**" ignores the fact that the **EU from its inception was not built to represent marginalised groups**.

Checklist Two: Using Gender Transformative Language

Language is constantly evolving, and it is okay if you do not always use the most transformative language. The following sections reflect discussions on progressive language from queer, disability, and racial justice activists. Reflecting on the terms you use and keeping up to date with best practices ensures your language is clear, inclusive and indicates to the reader your positionality.

Disability Language

It is always best to **follow the lead of people with disabilities** when using **disability-first or person-first language**. When writing reports, it is important to use language that is both **specific and not patronising**. For example, use **"blind person"** rather than "visually challenged". Similarly, you **should not reduce people to their disability aids**, e.g., somebody is a **"wheelchair user"** not "wheelchair-bound". **Avoid** using terms such as **"able-bodied"** which implies that people with disabilities have bodies that do not work. It is also a **common trend to refer to policy documents as "blind"** e.g., "the European Green Deal is gender-blind". **Avoid such language** and use terms such as **"does not account for"** or **"ignorant of"** instead.

Remember! It is our world that has never been made accessible for people with disabilities, the onus is not on those with disabilities themselves to conform to ableist structures.

Vulnerabilities Language

Avoid using terms such as "vulnerable people" or "poor people" that puts emphasis on people themselves. **No one is inherently vulnerable**; this language creates a **dichotomy of "us and them"**. **Structures of discrimination create vulnerable situations**. Calling someone vulnerable can also be used as a **domination technique** and diminish people's feeling of **agency**. Preferable terms to use instead are those that put emphasis on the structure: e.g., **people from marginalised groups, disproportionately affected groups, structurally excluded, or people living in vulnerable situations**.

Remember! When talking about aging groups "elderly" implies a dependency/inability and is often used to typecast whole generations, using older persons is preferred by activists.

Racialisation

Using the term **"racialised groups"** is preferable to "race" as it shows that race is socially constructed by highlighting the process of racialisation. **Equinox** defines **"racialised people"** as **"individuals and groups who have been subject to a process of racialisation and been ascribed a particular racial category"**. In European societies, **all people are racialised**, however we use the term to refer to those that have been **negatively racialised or racialised as "other"**.

Geographies

Describing the world through development discourse has **undergone a lot of changes**. **During the Cold War**, the terms **first, second and third world** were used to refer to the capitalist **coloniser** countries, **communist**, and **colonised** countries respectively. These descriptions have been criticised for creating a **heirarchy** between groups of countries. **After the Cold War**, the terms **Global North** and **South** became popular to describe countries that were **colonisers** versus those that **were colonised**, with **Global East** being used to describe the countries that were **subject to Russian imperialism**.

Core, periphery, and **semi-periphery** are **Marxist terms** that are used to describe how the **core countries colonised the periphery countries** in order to **violently extract wealth, resources and persons** from them for the core's own development. In this construction the **semi-periphery** is the **eastern European** countries which serve as a **reserve** for colonial extraction. Whilst the Cold War dynamics have shifted considerably, **these term is still used by some decolonial Marxists**.

Global Majority is a term used to describe **Black, Indigenous, and People of Colour** – who make up the **majority** of the **world's population**. **Global Minority** refers to **white** people, who despite being in the minority **violently dominate** with **white supremacy**.

Remember! It is important to discuss which framing you use whenever you are writing. Look at the context and see which framing you think applies best.

Non-Binary Language

Always write in gender neutral language, it is important to be **specific** about who you are speaking about and **highlight the social construction of gender**. For example, if you were writing a report about the gendered effects of toxic chemicals, you can write "**people who are assigned male or female at birth**". This highlights that we are **given a sex at birth** based on **sex characteristics** but that this **does not determine our gender**. Whereas terms like "**women**" refer to the **social elements** of a gendered group of individuals.

Remember! If you are writing a report and your data is only about women, it is not beneficial to tack onto the end "and nonbinary people/ marginalised genders" if this is not part of your analysis. Inclusion for the sake of it is not beneficial.

Avoiding saviourism and empowerment

When discussing empowerment, it is important **we do not use it as a buzzword**, for example **vague statements about 'empowering' groups** can often come from a **saviourist** standpoint which is not helpful. Additionally, **people cannot be empowered out of the structures that oppress them**, so any discussion of empowerment should be in **parallel with addressing such structures** otherwise the **onus is left on the individual**. "**Agents of change**" is an **alternative conceptualisation** to "empowerment". Recognising the agency of a person, means that you listen to what they have to say, and you **respect their experiences and knowledge**. An agent of change is working to **create systemic change** for themselves and their community. You cannot give a voice to someone who already has a voice, but you can **lend them your megaphone** and give them your seat at the decision-making table.

Remember! The images you use in a document are key signifiers and often reproduce power relations. It is important that you do not use tokenistic images i.e., using images of people from a marginalised community just to portray diversity that your work does not possess.

FURTHER READING

Equinox (2021) [Towards Gender Justice](#)

Gorman, J. (2024) [Beyond Extractivism in Research with Communities and Movements](#), The Commons Social Change Library

Decolonialidad Europa (2013) [Charter of Decolonial Research Ethics](#)

Sze, J.S., Cosmopolis, C., Hubbard, E.R.C., Mani, S., and Wang, M.M.H (2024) Challenging Colonial Practices in Research: A Guide for PhD Researchers, UK Research Integrity Office

Women Enabled International (2024) [Glossary](#)

Women Engage for a Common Future (2024) [Gender Glossary](#)

